

GAGE UNIVESITRY COLLEGE

SCHOOL OF GRADUATE STUDIES

DEPARTEMENT OF PROJECT MANAGEMENT

**FACTORS AFFECTING OF PROJECT FAILURE: THE CASE OF
DEVELOPMENT BANK OF ETHIOPIA**

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ADDIS ABABA, ETHIOPIA

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**A THESIS SUBMITTED TO GAGE UNIVERSITY COLLEGE,
SCHOOL OF GRADUATE STUDIES IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF
THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE DEGREE OF MASTERS OF ART IN
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DECLARATION

This thesis is my original work, prepared under the guidance of my Ph.D. advisor, Abebayehu H., and all sources used have been acknowledged. It has not been submitted to any higher institution for degree-granting purposes.

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Certification of approval of thesis

This is to certify that; the researcher has carried out this research work. This work is original in nature and submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the degree of master compile with the regulation of the university collage and meets the accepted standard with the regulation of the university collage and meet the accepted standard with respect to originality and quality

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DEDICATION

I dedicate this thesis manuscript to my father Ato Abishu Dejene and my mother w/o Tsehay Feleke, my Grandmother Ato Feleke Ababi and my brothers for their affection, love and dedicated partnership in the success of my life.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

<i>ABSTRACT</i>	XI
CHAPTER ONE	1
1. INTRODUCTION.....	1
1.1. Background of the study.....	1
1.2. Statement of the Problem	4
1.3. Research questions	6
1.4. Objectives of the Study	6
1.4.1. General Objective	6
1.4.2. Specific Objectives	6
1.5. Significance of the Study.....	6
1.6. Scope of the Study	7
1.7. Limitation of the study	7
1.8. Operational definition of key term this is includes	7
1.9. Organization of the paper	8
CHAPTER TWO	9
2. LITERATURE RELATED REVIEW	9
2.1. Theoretical Review	9
2.1.1. Theories of project management.....	9
2.1.2. Models of project management.....	11
2.1.3. Models of project failure and success	12
2.2. The Project Management Role	14
2.3. Empirical Literature Review.....	16
2.3.1. Project failure.....	16
2.4. Critical Failure Factors of the Project	18
2.4.1. Factors Relate to Management.....	19
2.4.2. Factors Related to Finance.....	19
2.4.3. Factors Related to Project.....	20
2.4.4. Factors Related to project Manager and Team Members.....	21
2.4.5. Factors Related to Organization.....	22
2.4.6. Factors Related to External Environment.....	22
2.4.7. Factors related to risk, culture and procurement process	23
2.5. Effect of Project specific factor on the failure project	25

2.6. Role of Credit management related causes of project failure.....	26
2.7. Effect of Macro Economical related causes of Project failure	27
2.8. Effect of Socio-political related causes of project failure	28
2.9. Literature Gap	28
2.10. Conceptual Framework	29
CHAPTER THREE	31
3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	31
3.1. INTRODUCTION.....	31
3.2. Description of the study area	31
3.3. Research Design and Research approach	31
3.3.1. Research design	31
3.3.2. Research Approach.....	32
3.4. Type and source of data.....	32
3.4.1. Primary Source	32
3.4.2. Secondary Source	33
3.5. Methods of Data collection.....	33
3.5.1. Questionnaire	33
3.5.2. Interviews	33
3.6. Sample design	34
3.6.2. Sample size determination and Sampling technique	34
3.7. Reliability and Validity	35
3.8. Data processing and analysis	35
3.8.1. Descriptive statistics	36
3.8.2. Inferential statistics	36
3.9. Model specification.....	36
3.10. Ethical consideration	37
CHAPTER FOUR.....	38
4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION	38
4.1. Introduction.....	38
4.2. Response Rate	38
4.3. Cuase for project failure the causes of development bank of Ethiopia financed projects,	43
4.4. Descriptive Statistics project specific factor.....	45
4.5. Descriptive Statistics Bank’s Credit Management factors	47
4.6 Socio-political Environment factors and project failure.....	49

4.7. Summary of Descriptive Statistics Responses on Independent and Dependent Variables	50
4.8. Correlation Analysis.....	51
4.9. Regression result	53
4.10. Regression model tests	54
4.11. Project specific factors and project failure	58
4.12. Bank’s credit management factor and project failure.....	59
4.13. Socio-political and environmental factor and project failure.....	60
4.14. General discussion.....	60
4.15. Summary of the regression analysis	64
4.16. Data Gathered from Conducted Interview.....	64
CHAPTER FIVE	66
5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS.....	66
5.1. Introduction.....	66
5.2. Conclusion	66
5.3. Recommendation	67
5.4. Implication for future research	69
References	70
Appendix I.....	I
Appendix II.....	VII

ABBREVIATION/ACRONOMY

ANOVA.....	Analysis of Variance
DBE.....	Development Bank of Ethiopia
GTP.....	Growth & Transformation Plan
NBE.....	National Bank of Ethiopia
PMBOK.....	Project Management Body of Knowledge
SPSS.....	Statistical package for Social Science
VIF.....	Variance Inflation Factor
WB.....	World Bank
SLM.....	Sustainable Land Management

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure: 2.1. Conceptual frameworks	30
Figure: 4.1. Work experience in the industry	43
Figure: 4.2. Heteroscedastic	54
Figure: 4.3. Test of normality	56

LIST OF TABLES

Table: 3.1. Respondents of Data Collection	34
Table: 3.2. Reliability test result Source: SPSS output.	35
Table: 4.1. Response rate.....	38
Table: 4.2. Gender of respondents	39
Table: 4.3. Education level of respondents.....	39
Table: 4.4. Age of respondents	40
Table: 4.5. Types of the project	40
Table: 4.6. Form of companies	41
Table: 4.7. Current position of respondents in the project/bank.....	41
Table: 4.8. Respondent religious	42
Table: 4.9. Respondent martial statutes.....	42
Table: 4.10. The participantS work experience in the industry	43
Table: 4.11. Descriptive analysis 5-point Likert type scale,.....	44
Table: 4.12. Project specific factor.	45
Table: 4.13. Descriptive Statistics of bank’s Credit Management factors.....	47
Table: 4.15. Descriptive Statistics Socio-political Environment factors	49
Table: 4.16. Summary of Descriptive Statistics.....	50
Table: 4.17. Correlation.....	51
Table: 4.18. Regression result.....	53
Table: 4.19. Multi co-linearity	55
Table: 4.20. Model Summary	56
Table: 4.21. ANOVA ^a	57
Table: 4.22. Model Summary	58
Table: 4.23. Coefficients	58
Table: 4.22. Summary of regression analysis	64

ABSTRACT

Worldwide, (Global) project failure is a widespread occurrence caused by a variety of external as well as internal factors. The primary objective of this study is to factors affecting of project failure in Ethiopia's Development Bank. For the study, a both descriptive and explanatory study approach was selected. About 96 projects from the mining, agriculture, and industrial sectors make up the target population for this study, which used a census sample strategy in addition to a quantitative and qualitative research approach. A questionnaire that was self-administered was used to gather primary data. SPSS version 26 was used to code and analyze the data. To determine whether fluctuations in the independent variables could account for changes in the dependent variable, a multiple liner regression model was built. The findings demonstrate that a number of independent variables, including project failure, characteristics specific to the project, factors linked to the bank's credit management, and variables connected to socio-politics, have a substantial impact on project failure in the context of the Ethiopian Development Bank of Ethiopia. There is a positive correlation between every independent variable and every project failure. The bank needs to be required to thoroughly evaluate initiatives. Additionally, the Bank will strengthen project follow-up and technical advice while addressing issues related to appraisal reports and incorporating a contingency budget plan into the project cost determination. In order to safeguard the project from destruction and looting, as well as to provide support during periods of political and social unrest, the government, the bank, and the project owner should educate the public about its benefits.

Key words: political and social problems, bank credit management factors, project failure, and project-specific factors.

CHAPTER ONE

1. INTRODUCTION

This chapter begins with research background to give an idea about the area of the paper to the reader. This is followed by background of the study, the statement of the problem, Research objective, and significance of the study, scope of the study operational definition of key terms and finally organization of the study.

1.1. BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Harold (2009), defined a project as any series of activities and tasks that have a specific objective to be completed within certain specifications, defined start and end dated, funding limits (if applicable) Consume human and nonhuman resources (i.e., money, people, equipment, are multifunctional (i.e. cut across several functional lines). A project is a temporary endeavor undertaken to create a unique product, service or result. The temporary nature of projects indicates that a project has a definite beginning and end. Project management is the application of knowledge, skills, tools and techniques to project activities to meet the project requirements (PMBOK, 2013).

Previously, different researches have been conducted related to causes of project failure and cost and schedule performance of projects. For project, failure there is no commonly accepted definition. Different authors define project failure from different perspective and context. (According to Carlos2002), cited by Mwangi (2015), a project is considered as failed when it has not delivered what was required, in line with expectations. Therefore, in order to succeed, a project must deliver utilizing the minimum cost possible, the expected quality, and on the time scheduled and it must deliver the benefits presented in the business scale. In the most general sense, failures can occur in three circumstances. First, something that is expected to happen does not happen. Second, something that will be expected not to happen does happen. Third, something happens that was not considered at all, Kusek, (2013). Addo, & Choudhury, (2012), the project size, clarity of objectives, the proportion of funding from abroad, and political conditions have significant effects on the rate of implementation of externally assisted development projects in Africa. An increase in project size by \$1 million will lead to a 0.04 decrease in the implementation rate of project.

Patrick (2015) the government of Malawi, in 2001, through the then Ministry of Irrigation and Water Development secured funding amounting to UA 9.67 million from African Development Bank (ADB) to implement the Horticulture and Food Crops Development Project. However, the HFCDP did not meet its aims and objectives and is a typical example of big projects that have failed in the agriculture sector. Arrow (1998), cited by Matu, (2020), in analyzing project failure factors for Kenya Rail ways projects, identified poor communication, little experience of the project manager late procurement of equipment, lack of training of project managers and slow project selection methods has been the major causes of project failure Yilkal, (2015). When the weighted average recruitment variation of the projects work force in terms of number, qualification and experience are increased by 1% from below the plan, which is stated in the Banks appraisal document project failure, was increased by 10.7%. Development Bank of Ethiopia (DBE) as one of the development institutions in the country is a financial institution established to support the economic development of the country by providing project finance, in particular the bank provides medium- and long-term loan finance to encourage private sector investment of commercial agriculture, Agro processing, manufacturing and mining industries for projects that support socio-economic development of the country. The selected sectors, which are financed by the bank, are government priority areas, Hence, DBE support is mainly focused at the national goal to accelerate the progress of the countries development effort to bring sustained economic growth. In order to meet this core objective, projects that are financed by the bank should be successful or achieve the objective for which they are established. According to annual performance of the Bank (2013) project success is evaluated using different dimensions including employment creation, tax payment to the government, percentage of generating foreign currency, local raw materials consumption, Agro processing and technology transfer for the local economy. Ethiopia is amongst the fastest growing non-oil economies in the world that has recorded double digit growth for the last decade. This strong economic growth has been highly attributed to the country's public sector-led development strategy. In GTPII special emphasis is given to Agriculture, Manufacturing, Rural development, Infrastructure development, Human development and good governance (DBE five-year strategic reform plan, 2019).

Financial institutions were assumed to play a key role in materializing GTP II by providing credit service, trade service and stabilizing macro-economic environments. The Development Bank of Ethiopia (DBE) is one of the two state-owned banks entrusted with the objectives of medium and long-term financing of development projects in the agricultural, Agro processing, manufacturing industry, and mining and extractive industry sectors. Over the past 10 years, the Bank disbursed over Birr 48.8 billion to different development projects. According to (development bank of Ethiopia five-year strategic reform plan, 2019) Just in 2017/18 alone, it disbursed Birr 7 billion (development bank of Ethiopia annual report, 2018). However, recently, different examinations reports, including supervision reports of the NBE, indicate that almost all prudential and financial indicators of the Bank have continuously deteriorated pushing it to near insolvency. At appraisal stage, eligibility of the promoter for Bank finance, and technical feasibility, financial viability, institutional capacity, socio-economic benefits and environmental soundness of the project are evaluated. If the project is found to be sound through these evaluations, the Bank approves a loan according to the financial requirement of the project. Under implementation stage; the Bank intervenes through frequent and serious inspection in order to ensure the utilization of the finance for the intended purposes and project are being implemented according to planned schedules. After implementation, the Bank continues monitoring and evaluation of projects through its follow-up operation until the project fully repaid the loan. The main purposes of the follow-up operations are to evaluate project performance with respect to project plan, to propose corrective measures whenever there is deviation from plan, to enhance collection, and provide feedback for future appraisal process (development bank of Ethiopia credit policy,2018).

There is no generally common consensus what project failure entails. However, in the awake of such ambiguity, some scholars have come up with what project failure implies. Standish Group International (2014) study defines project failure as projects completed and operation with over budget, over scheduled time and offers fewer features and functions than originally specified. Another thought indicates that „a project that achieves the planned outcomes within the allocated time, scope, quality and budget constraints could still be perceived as a failed project“ Belassi and Turkel, (1996).

According to Cusworth and Franse (1983), project failure can be identifying at two levels: -

- I. Failure at implementation stage to complete on time, within the budget and in line with the plan.
- II. Failure that occurs when implementation has been completed but fails to deliver the entire intended objective. The current research focuses on project failure at the two levels.

1.2. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Now days, due to different reasons, project failure is common and worldwide phenomenon, which affects the overall economies of the countries especially on developing countries. Management problem, implementation problem, market problem, technical failure, quality of man-power problem, missing objectives, follow up level /technical support given by the bank, overestimation of project return and manpower quality of projects, problems of corruption and related cause, continuous rise of product price, raw materials price and wages, intervention of political leaders on project, government officials perception towards the project and change in economic policies were the case for development bank of Ethiopia financed projects failure at Dessie District (Alex , 2018), the study restricted to only Dessie District; hence, further research is required at another location.

According to Ika, & Saint-Macary, (2014), to sum up, our initial understanding is that projects in Africa do not succeed solely due to mismanagement but also due to the intricate nature of their specific project environments. More specifically, projects do not succeed because of in adequate project management abilities or expertise, as well as corruption, inadequate policy planning and execution, and the intricate circumstances surrounding them. The reassuring news is that in fields such as ICT and in nations such as South Africa, project management is progressing in the correct direction. In terms of project management procedures and business outcomes, performance rates are increasing.

Adamu (2013), identified from the macroeconomic variables, the proxy measure of exchange rate, project cost overrun is statistically significant. As per his study population size and literacy level in which the project's operating area has factors for project failure. Running of projects with lower number of workers, educational background and experience stated in appraisal report is the major cause for development bank of Ethiopia financed project failure.

Alex (2018) has also conducted research to identify Causes of Failure of Projects financed by Development Bank of Ethiopia, the Case of Dessie District. As per his finding management problem, market and marketing problems and delay in project implementation are the major project specific related factor of project failure.

From the credit management factors follow up level appraisals of project using current price, over estimation of return from project and project planning capacity of the financers are major factor to a project to fail.

Research showed that, some project specific explanatory variables, such as marketing problem and human resource recruitment variation in aggravating project failure, but project implementation time overrun to decrease project failure. Moreover, development bank of Ethiopia's project planning capacity and exchange rate change are found statistically significant in increasing project failure from development bank of Ethiopia's credit management and macroeconomic explanatory variables respectively. Among sociopolitical variables, population size and literacy level in which the projects are working are found to be statistically significant in decreasing project failure as both variables increasing.

Adamu (2013), the study considered 120 and above projects through stratified sampling method from projects financed and which were operational for at least one year and identified major factors of failure for development bank of Ethiopia financed projects.

However, according to Cusworth and Franks, (2013). Projects can be failed at both analyze the major causes for project failure at both level and to check the result of Adamu (2013), with the time gap of 8 years. As per the secondary data collected from the Development Bank of Ethiopia, regular project follows up reports and annual reports most of the financed projects cannot meet its plan regarding loan repayment, implementation schedule and required additional loan due to the Impact war and of Corona Virus, the impact of this variable did not identify so far. Moreover, it is common to see foreclosure advertisement of development bank of Ethiopia on different mass media following the failure of projects to repay their debts. This situation created a bad image on the public about development bank of Ethiopia finance by mis perceiving that credit management system of the Bank as the main factor for project failure. Moreover, previous studies have not examined on loan status indicates that how the problem is serious and needs critical study. In this study, the role of these variable was examined. To bridge all mentioned gapes and problems the researcher is excited to conduct this research.

In an attempt to contribute in bridging the above stated problems, this study focused on factor affecting for project failure in Development bank of Ethiopia.

1.3. RESEARCH QUESTION

In order to access and analyze the variables that have significant contribution to project failure, the following questions have been address in their search.

1. What is the project specific failure factor of development bank of Ethiopia projects?
2. What is the Bank credit management failure factor of development bank of Ethiopia projects?
3. What is the socio-political and environment failure factor of development bank of Ethiopia project?

1.4. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1.4.1. GENERAL OBJECTIVE

The main objectives of the study were to the factors affecting for project failure in case of development bank of Ethiopia head quarter Addis Ababa.

1.4.2. SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study was the following specific objectives: -

1. To assess project specific factors of project failure financed by DBE.
2. To identify the bank credit management factor, cause of failure of DBE projects.
3. To examine the socio-political environment factor causes of failure of DBE financed projects.

1.5. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Different conducted researches indicate; that Project failure is wide phenomena around the world. Development Bank of Ethiopia has been providing loan for projects, which are under government priority area. However, due to different reasons, some projects failed at the implementation phase and others after commissioning. To this end, most of financed projects could not generate the expected socio-economic benefits. Thus, the study is very essential to assess with this regard. Identifying the most significant factors for the project failure and it is very important to provide policy recommendations with regard to project failure. Furthermore, this study was as a literature for further researches to be conduct by academicians and researchers with similar topics.

1.6. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

Development Bank of Ethiopia has a long year “ experience in long, medium- and short-term project financing in different sectors and which have significant contribution to the country’s development. However, it has hindered different problems on those financed projects when they are under implementation stage and after fully commissioned. The area of the study was limited to the topic of Project Failure Factors and the project management framework around which most projects are planned. This framework embodies the factors related to Management, Finance related, Project related, Project Manager related, Project team members related, Organization related, External environment related and factors related to risk, culture and procurement. Hence, the study focuses on the Manufacturing, Agricultural and Mining projects financed by the bank from the year 2017 up to 2023. For project failure on development of Ethiopia financed projects the study focuses on the head office only

1.7. LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

The researcher believes that the following are limitation bearing on the quality of the research findings. Those are Limited collaboration from different stakeholders, Lack of related literatures, the study area was limited to development bank of Ethiopia financed projects and the research data was collected from failed project staffs and employees of development bank of Ethiopia at Head Office. Due to lack of data, other banks do not select as a sample. Because of this, the study was only considering from published materials by various scholars abroad and employees “point of view about Cause for project frailer. However, your scope says, the study focuses on the Manufacturing, Agricultural and Mining projects financed by the bank from the year 2017 up to 2023.

1.8. OPERATIONAL DEFINITION OF KEY TERM THIS IS INCLUDES

1: Project failure is a situation when a given project, which consumes human, material land financial resources, fails to deliver an acceptable return on investment, so it is terminated before the completion, no sufficient value is produced, and no benefit is delivered to the customer. Development Bank of Ethiopia (development bank of Ethiopia)- is specialized financial institutions established to support the economic development of the country by providing medium- and long-term loan to encourage private sector investment.

2: The project specific factors project implementation delay, management problems and quality of products and marketing problems have no significant impact for project failure in the case of Development Bank of Ethiopia projects.

3: Bank's credit management practice good appraisal, on time fund release and proper project follow up are not significant factors of projects failure in the case of Development Bank of Ethiopia projects.

4: Socio- political environment and social unrest and occurrence of Corona virus pandemic have no significant impact for project failure in the case of Development Bank of Ethiopia financed projects.

1.9. ORGANIZATION OF THE PAPER

This research study organized under five chapters. The first chapter presents the introduction, which includes the background, statement of the problem, objectives, significance, scope and operational definition of key terms, of the study. The second chapter provides the review of relevant literatures that is pertinent to the topic. Chapter three explains about the research method used, which includes the research area, research design, unit of analysis, targeted population, sample size and sampling technique, sampling frame the sources of data and method of data collection and analysis. In chapter, four result and discussion presented and conclusion and recommendation were discussed under chapter five.

CHAPTER TWO

2. LITERATURE RELATED REVIEW

2.1. THEORETICAL REVIEW

This section reviews the literature written by different authors in relation to causes for project failure. Therefore, this section has two parts, which are the theoretical literature and empirical literature, and also Literature gap identification that inspired the researcher was analyzed and finally the conceptual frame work will to identify. Adapted by the author from the above literature (2022/23).

2.1.1. THEORIES OF PROJECT MANAGEMENT

Project Management is the planning, organizing, directing, and controlling of company resources for a relatively short-term objective that has been established to complete specific goals and objectives (Harold, 2009).

Koskela, & Howell, (2002) we have provided empirical evidence and theoretical explanations to suggest that current project management doctrine has serious theoretical underpinnings. First, it is based on a misunderstanding of the nature of project work and incorrect definitions of planning, execution and control Second, a theoretical foundation was implied. Arguably, these deficiencies led to three types of problems. First, project management has not achieved its goal: it does not work satisfactorily in small, simple and slow-moving projects; theoretical problems can be solved informally and without more penalties that are generous. In today's large, complex and fast-paced projects, traditional project management is simply counterproductive; creates self-inflicted problems that are very detrimental to work.

Second, the lack of them or made education and training difficult and hindered the effective professionalization of project management in the absence of theory, project management cannot claim a permanent and respected place in higher education. In addition, the lack of a theoretical explanation of project management has slowed down the diffusion of project management techniques into practice. Third, project management innovation is hampered by a lack of theory Anomalies, deviations from theory-predicted results in project management have been observed for a long time, but their cause was not understood and the project management community did not act accordingly. The important functions of the theory, related to the continuous verification of validity and the direction of further progress, have not been realized either in research or in practice.

The current evidence is strong enough to argue that a paradigmatic transformation of the project management discipline is needed the necessary transformation means that a closer relationship between theory and practice must be created in project management Theory and practice must be developed simultaneously, similar to other science-based fields where theory is clarified, tested and refined through ongoing dialogue between the scientific and professional communities. According to, PMBOOK (2013) divides project management into the following knowledge areas:

- **Project Integration Management:** includes the processes and activities needed to identify, define, combine, unify, and coordinate the various processes and project management activities within the Project Management Process Groups.
- **Project Scope Management:** includes the processes required to ensure that the project includes all the work required, and only the work required, to complete the project successfully.
- **Project Time Management:** includes the processes required to manage the timely completion of the project. It is about tracking our schedule.
- **Project Cost Management:** includes the processes involved in planning, estimating, budgeting, financing, funding, managing, and controlling costs so that the project can be completed within the approved budget.
- **Project Quality Management:** includes the processes and activities of the performing organization that determine quality policies, objectives, and responsibilities so that the project will satisfy the needs for which it was undertaken.
- **Project Human Resource Management:** includes the processes that organize, manage, and lead the project team.
- **Project Communications Management:** includes the processes that are required to ensure timely and appropriate planning, collection, creation, distribution, storage, retrieval, management, control, monitoring, and the ultimate disposition of project information.
- **Project Risk Management:** includes the processes of conducting risk management planning, identification, analysis, response planning, and controlling risk on a project.
- **Project Procurement Management:** includes the processes necessary to purchase or acquire products, services, or results needed from outside the project team.

- **Project Stakeholder Management:** - includes the processes required to identify all people or organizations impacted by the project, analyzing stakeholder expectations and impact on the project, and developing appropriate management strategies for effectively engaging stakeholders in project decisions and execution.

2.1.2. MODELS OF PROJECT MANAGEMENT

According to Lalmi, et al (2021) The proposed hybrid project management model remains generic, several other practices can be applied to develop this model, exploring various lean design practices in the design phase, lean construction tools and techniques in the execution phase, integrating integrated project delivery (IPD) practices.) throughout the project life cycle and using collaborative agility tools and techniques, while maintaining the best practices of the traditional approach that under pins this model, the level of use of the hybrid approach tools and practices varies from project to project. A project depends on different project-related parameters, as project management is highly dependent on, agile thinking increases productivity and maximizes results, and agile training can foster collaboration and flexibility in teams. In practice, the model should be effective and only the effectiveness of the project team and overall customer satisfaction. The proposed tools and techniques can be developed by studying the applicability of each tool and technique to the construction context. Validation of this model will be necessary to confirm the results of this study.

Monteiro, et al (2016) we analyzed several PMO models from the literature the results show that PMO structures, roles, functions and descriptions vary widely across sources. Indeed, the authors identify many different PMOs In the literature search, we identified a total of 47 PMO models, but some models share the same name, reducing the number of unique models to 25 All authors propose three, four or five PMO models In many cases, the position of the PMO in a hierarchical organization (strategic, silent, or operational) determines the degree of authority, adoption, acceptance, and autonomy to define, disseminate, and support project management practices somewhere within the company. The progression of PMO appears to be gradual from low to high decision making. In this article, we limit the data presentation to current PMO snapshots. We know that more advanced analysis is needed and this is already planned for the next step of our research for example, no attempt has been made to identify similarities between the features of each model presented here. This analysis will be developed in future work and will help to assemble some of the proposed models.

2.1.3. MODELS OF PROJECT FAILURE AND SUCCESS

According to Radujković, and Sjekavica, (2017), Project management is inevitable in today's world, a place of continuous improvement in the implementation of many different projects. Project management is not only a necessity for that improvement, but also a field that seeks improvement itself, influencing various PM success factors. These factors have been examined in this article as a frame work for the breakdown of project management success factors. The breakdown structure is the applied to three different EU co-financed projects and conclusions are drawn, them oust important of which are related to their conciliation of the proposed break down structure methodology with the actual trends and states of the projects. It is necessary to invest in project management, especially in strengthening the skills of people and organizations. This article discusses project success and failure, project classification, and factors that contributed to project success and project failure. The results of the case study and feedback from 50 students reflect agreement on some of the factors that led to project failure. In addition, poor planning and scheduling are the main causes of project failure other important things that cannot be overlook are the quality of the team leaders and the friendliness of the team members.

This is clearly seen in the success of the projects of teams 1, 2, 3 and 4. Three key factors for project success are user involvement, good planning and evaluation, and good leadership and technical skills of team members. Comparing the results of the case study with the Standish group report, it is clear that these factors are fundamental and strongly influence the failure of many projects. Applying good project management practices would help avoid these failure factors and lead to project success. Attarzadeh, IirkO,SH(2008) according to Zuofa,& Ochieng,(2014), This paper examined the failures of selected projects in Nigeria the relevance of the topic is understood in light of Nigeria's decision on the failure of the project. He also stated that the projects and their implementation are among the thematic objectives of the ongoing transformation agenda in Nigeria. The results confirmed that, as in other climates, project management professionals in Nigeria are still divided on project failure and success. Specifically, it was recognized that practitioners perceive project failure to be due to a variety of factors, not just the inability to execute and deliver projects within set costs, timelines, or goals. Essentially, this means that a comprehensive understanding of project failure can only come from activities carried out during the project life cycle and from stakeholders' definitions and criteria.

However, it is worth noting that based on the unanimous opinions of the focus group discussion, corruption, unprofessionalism, in experienced project managers and project staff, bureaucratic procurement process was cited as the main reasons for project failure in Nigeria the findings also highlighted the need to implement governance mechanisms that integrate processes and guidelines to help projects achieve their organizational goals. It has also suggested that criminal action should be taken against erring project workers who engage in corrupt and unethical practices one caveat is that the paper had some limitations that need to be considered in the future an important limitation was the number of participants in the focus group another limitation was the choice of a purely qualitative methodological approach. Future research may consider using quantitative analyzes to identify any relationships among identified causes of project failure in Nigeria Even with these limitations, the paper's findings still have important implications and thoughts for future projects in Nigeria and other countries facing similar challenges Zuofa, & Ochieng, (2014).

In the past, there have been several studies on the causes of project failure and on project costs and performance planning. There is noun inversely accepted definition of project failure. Different authors define project failure from different angles and contexts. According to Carla (2002), a project is considered to have failed when it did not do what it was asked to do as expected. Therefore, for the project to be successful, it must be delivered at the lowest possible cost, with high quality and on time; and must deliver the benefits presented in the business case. In the most general sense, failures can occur in three circumstances. First, something that is expected to happen does not happen. Second, something that was expected not to happen does happen. Third, something happens that was not considered at all, (2013). For the past twenty years ago, successful projects defined as the completion of an activity within the constraints of time, cost, and performance (HAROLD K, 2009). According to HAROLD. K (2009) currently, the definition of project success has been modified to include completion within the allocated time period, within the budgeted cost, at the proper performance or specification level, with acceptance by the customer/user, with minimum or mutually agreed upon scope changes, without disturbing the main work flow of the organization and without changing the corporate culture.

The Ethiopian Foreclosure law (*proclamation* number 97/1998, Article3) states that the bank financed business can be considered as failed and foreclosed when a Bank's claims are not paid within the time stipulated in the contract.

This definition is also contextually similar with McConnell definition that says projects are considered as failed if not produce results as proposed or expected, because Bank financed projects are expected to settle their debt as per loan contract agreement. Similarly, the nonperforming loan directive of National Bank of Ethiopia Number SBB/48/2010 stipulates that those financed projects failed to pay the due loans for more than three years to be classified also loan and obliged the bank to hold 100% provision. Considering the above definition of project failure in to consideration, DBE defines successful as properly meet their debt services, performing above their breakeven point, meeting their objectives by generating tax revenue to the government, employment opportunity and generate or save foreign currency otherwise to be considered as failed according to (DBE procedural manual, 2014). DBE definition of project success includes meeting of project objective in addition to expectation of fulfilling debt obligation that stipulated in foreclosure law and non-performing directives since the strategic mission of DBE goes far more than loan collection fulfill release development partner. The success of projects financed by DBE, therefore, highly required from the point of overall contribution to the national economic growth.

2.2. THE PROJECT MANAGEMENT ROLE

Project management is defined as the knowledge, skills, tools and techniques to project activities to meet the project requirements (PMBOK, 2013, p. 554). Project management is the discipline of carefully projecting or planning, organizing, motivating and controlling resources to achieve specific goals and meet specific success criteria. An official definition of project management, courtesy of the Project Management Institute, defines the term as: “the application of knowledge, skills, tools and techniques to project activities to meet project requirements.” Project management is the discipline of planning, organizing and managing resources to bring about the successful completion of specific project goals. Project management is accomplished through the application and integration of the project management processes of initiating, planning, executing, monitoring and controlling, and closing” (PMBOK 2004, p. 8). Project management is a set of principles, methods, and techniques that people use to effectively plan and control project work. It establishes a sound basis for effective planning, scheduling, resourcing, decision making, controlling, and re-planning. Project management principles and techniques help complete projects on schedule, within budget, and in full accordance with project specifications. At the same time, they help achieve the other goals of the organization, such as productivity, quality, and cost effectiveness. The objective of project management is to optimize project cost, time, and quality.

The application of modern management techniques and systems to the execution of a project from start to finish, to achieve predetermined objectives of scope, quality, time and cost, to the equal satisfaction of those involved.

Essentially, project management is a set of skills and tools that will help you get the project right in every way. A project manager is assigned to a project to guide the team so that they can achieve the project objectives. The project manager is the link between the project team and the project plan, and his/her task is to satisfy both the team and the task needs. The project manager is another key stakeholder in the project and his competence is a critical factor affecting project planning, scheduling, and communication (Belassi and Tukel 1996). Variables under this factor consist of the skills and characteristics of project managers, their commitment, competence, experience, and authority (Chua et al. 1999).

Team needs might be group and/or individual needs. Knowledge, performance and personal skills are competences that are required for a project manager. Effective project managers require a balance of ethical, interpersonal, and conceptual skills that help them analyze situations and interact appropriately (PMBOK, 2013, p. 17). Great leadership is therefore often of high importance so that the project team will work together towards achieving the project objective. The project manager must play an important role when motivating the team members.

Anantatmula also states that a project manager should seek to create clarity and open communication in the project team. (Anantatmula, 2010, p. 19-20). It is essential for the project manager to be able to create an effective work environment so that the project team is suited to meet the challenges they experience in the global economy today (Anantatmula, 2010, p. 13). It is reasonable to assume that in project management, it is not if the plans will change, it is when, what will change, and by how much". The project manager's leadership role is also assumed to be of higher importance when there are big changes in a project. Larson and Gray (2011, p. 533) states that project managers usually face different problems when working internationally. However, there is no specific framework concerning this topic. Success or failure of a project is often influenced by how the project managers approach problems that might occur. (Larson and Gray, pp. 533-558). International projects might consist of cultural differences such as values and beliefs. It is also important for the project manager to understand the importance of language and meanings so that communication will be understood and interpret in the right way by the project team. (Javernick-Will & Scott, 2010, p. 554).

Zeng, Xie, Tam and Sun (2009, p. 61) states that cultural diversity is one important factor to international project management, and that it is therefore also important for project managers to implement cross cultural management.

Some can see cultural differences as negative; however, others also experience it as an essential part of growth in the organization and for individuals (Zeng, Xie, Tam and Sun 2009, p. 61). Zen, Xie, Tam and Sun (2009, p. 62) also define that “In a cross-cultural organization, changes in personnel, clientele, product line, financial climate, and even corporate philosophy and/or vision will happen. Cross-cultural awareness facilitates successful performance of a set task”. Project managers working in an international environment tend to experience challenges in relation to project delivery, knowledge and experience in cross cultural management is therefore important in regards to project success. Hong, Snell and Easter by-Smith (2006, p. 423) states that project managers that work with international project teams should create awareness in regards to cultural differences and that identifying the different cultures represented is a key component in project management. Project management reduces risk and increases the chance of success. A triangle, commonly called the triple constraint, is used to summarize project management. The triple constraint has four core elements: Projects must be within cost, on time, within scope and must meet customer quality requirements.

2.3. EMPIRICAL LITERATURE REVIEW

2.3.1. PROJECT FAILURE

Most of the early studies in the area focused on the reasons for project failure rather than project success. It is assumed that if a project’s completion time exceeded its due date, or expenses overran the budget, or outcomes did not satisfy a company's predetermined performance criteria, the project was assumed to be a failure. Delays in project completion times are common. Because of the delays, project managers sometimes pay penalties which increase overall project costs (Wallid Bellasi 1999 Vol. 14, No. 3, pp. 141-151,). There are many writers who tells why projects fail. For instance, Field tells us that projects fail too often because the project scope was not fully appreciated and/or user needs not fully understood. Hulme said that projects and associated procurements take place in an environment characterized by the following: Lack of management continuity and an incentive system that encourages overly optimistic estimates of the benefits that can be attained from doing the project. And Leicht said that high user expectations can actually be the cause of project failure. Hoffman says that projects fail because of poor alignment between departments and project users.

And in another article Hoffman tells us that project managers too often act as “process cops and report compilers and lose sight of what they’re supposed to be doing to make sure projects are running effectively. In a 2003 article Julia King reports, projects fail on average.

Now if you are an extremely optimistic person, you might conclude the good news is that 70% of these projects succeed. But note that King does not tell us how many of the 70% of the successful projects were over budget, over time, or defective in function upon completion. The purpose of this study is to identify project failure factors and identify the effects of the factors on project performance. Thus, instead of analyzing individual factors, one would first be able to the group a factor belongs to, and then determine the combined effects of these factors in eventually leading to project failure. The success and failure factors were first introduced by Rubin and Sealing in 1967. They investigated the impact of a project manager's experience on the project's success or failure. Technical performance was used as a measure of success. It was concluded that a project manager's previous experience has minimal impact on the project's performance, whereas the size of the previously managed project does affect the manager's performance.

Rubin and Sealing’s study was followed by a theoretical study by Avots. He identified reasons for project failure and concluded that the wrong choice of project manager, the unplanned project termination and unsupportive top management were the main reasons for failure. In 1983 Baker, Murphy and Fisher suggested that instead of using time, cost and performance as measures for project success, perceived performance should be measure.

Hughes conducted a survey to identify the factors that affect project performance. He concluded that projects fail because of improper basic managerial principles, such as the improper focus of the management system, by rewarding the wrong actions, and the lack of communication of goals. In their book, Morris and Hough studied eight large, complex projects which had great potential economic impact but were poorly managed and generally failed. They identified the failure factors for each of them. One of the first efforts to classify critical factors was carried out by Schultz, Slevin and Pinto. They classified factors as strategic or tactical. These two groups of factors affect project performance at different phases of implementation. The strategic group includes factors such as project mission, top management support and project scheduling whereas the tactical group consists of factors such as client consultation, personnel selection and training. In their follow-up work, Pinto and Slevin identified success factors, and their relative importance, for each stage of a research and development project life cycle.

In addition to the literature described above the researcher referred to project management books by Locke, Meredith, Mantel, and by Martin for further discussions on critical failure factors.

2.4. CRITICAL FAILURE FACTORS OF THE PROJECT

The framework in Figure 3 addresses many of the drawbacks in the literature. The researcher grouped the factors into eight areas:

1. Factors Related to Management
2. Factors Related to Finance
3. Factors Related to the Project,
4. Factors Related to the Project Manager,
5. Factors Related to the Project Team Members,
6. Factors Related to the Organization,
7. Factors Related to the External Environment,
8. Factors Related to risk, culture and procurement process,

As can be seen from the figure, the groups are interrelated. A factor in one group can influence a factor in another group, and a combination of several factors from various groups might lead to project failure.

For instance, top management support is a factor related to an organization which can be affected by the general state of the economy. Similarly, the uniqueness of project activities can affect the project manager's competence on the job. Lack of top management support together with the project manager's lack of competence on the job might lead to project failure. One of the advantages of grouping the factors in this fashion is that although it might be difficult to identify the failure factors specific to certain industries or organizations, it might be easier to identify whether the failure is related to the project manager and/or to the project and/or to external factors. Note that these four groups offer a comprehensive set in that any factor listed in the literature, or even specific points of consideration, should belong to at least one group. The framework suggest here not only brings advantages by grouping critical factors, but also helps project managers understand the intra-relationships between the factors in different groups. For instance, in the literature the availability of resources is considered to be a factor necessary for the successful completion of projects. Here, however, the studies suggest that resource availability is a systems response to organizational, environmental and project management-related factors such as top management support, project managers' negotiation skills and the general economic situation.

This will help project managers evaluate and monitor their projects more accurately. Similarly, project managers' competence is a critical factor that affects project planning, scheduling and communication.

Thus, effective planning, scheduling and communication are really not factors but immediate effects of factors related to a project manager, such as his managerial skills, competence and his technical background. Using this framework, project managers can easily observe these cause effect relationships. Furthermore, they can easily adapt this framework to their specific situations and include the factors that were found to be critical for their project's success. As will be explained in the next section, many project managers and managers involved in projects find this framework to be a better tool for understanding critical success factors.

2.4.1. FACTORS RELATE TO MANAGEMENT

A fundamental assumption of project management practice and research is that using project management to achieve organizational objectives improves organizational performance. This assumption is so ingrained that it appears to be self-evident; if it were otherwise, there would be little reason to justify the considerable expense that many organizations go to in developing and maintaining project management systems and certifying staff in external standards. There would also be little reason to justify the not inconsiderable intellectual effort applied by academics and researchers around the world to develop and refine project management theory and practice.

A wide variety of authors comment that project management has a positive effect on aspects of an organization's success. Whether this is broadly expressed in terms of the impact on overall productivity (Cleland, 1984; McHugh & Hogan, 2011), performance (Abbasi & Al-Mharmah, 2000), efficiency (Stimpson, 2008), or effectiveness (Shenhar, Dvir, Levy, & Maltz, 2001), the underlying assumption is that it is good business to use project management to achieve organizational objectives. However, this assumption typically remains unexamined.

2.4.2. FACTORS RELATED TO FINANCE

Financial Management on project performance will be one of the key challenges for corporations in the next decade: only those institutions that have sound financial structures and stable income flows will be able to fulfill their multiple missions and respond to the current challenges in an increasingly complex and global environment Anthony and Young (2003). Indeed, financial management is not an end in itself; it aims to ensure an organization's goals are reached by guaranteeing that the institution produces sufficient income to enable it to invest in its future.

Unsustainable project operations can be accommodated for either by developing sustainable operations or by planning for a future lacking in resources currently required. In practice organizations mostly tend to aim towards sustainability by increasing efficiency in the way in which resources are utilized.

Financial management checks under review in this proposal will include: budgeting, banking and expenditure checks Strogatz (2003). Organizations are facing challenges regarding their budgeting in project management. Pressure to follow through with only the projects that are going to be successful and carry less risk is mounting. As a project manager one needs to keep budgeting queries and be aware of benefits at all times throughout the project (Bourne and Walker, 2003).

Good financial and accounting systems are paramount: it is essential that management has current, accurate, and relevant financial data to ensure sound decision-making. Internal controls should be robust and should be rigorously overseen Anthony and Young (2003). According to Habeeb, (2013) financial management is the operation of an internal control system. Financial management of projects must be actively managed; it is an important part of the project management process and should be reviewed by the project manager, financial team, stakeholders and key project team members regularly (Weick, 2005; Backström, 2004; Jensen, 2004; van Eijnatten, 2003). By keeping a close eye on the project budgets, one will be assured that they are kept within the forecast set from the beginning.

2.4.3. FACTORS RELATED TO PROJECT

Project characteristics have long been overlooked in the literature as being critical failure factors whereas they constitute one of the essential dimensions of project performance. Among the few studies, Morris and Hough II identified schedule duration and urgency as critical factors. Many projects, however, fail due to several other factors inherent in projects• The size and the value of a project, the uniqueness of project activities (vs. standard activities), the density of a project network, project life cycle and the urgency of a project outcome• In a recent study by Tukul and Rom, it was found that the durations of many large size projects, those with more than 100 activities, exceed their deadlines.

There are usually penalties imposed on projects when deadlines are exceeded. Monetary penalties and loss of credibility are the most common ones. Thus, if the project lifespan is being used as a measure to evaluate project performance, one should be cautious about the size of a project and the effectiveness of the penalties. Not only the number of activities but also the familiarity of the organization with the type of project being undertaken is critical.

The project manager's performance on the job can be heavily influenced by the uniqueness of the activities.

The more standard activities a project has, the easier it is for project managers to plan, schedule and monitor their projects. Another characteristic which needs to be emphasized is project density. This is defined as the ratio of total number of precedence relationships to the total number of activities. The allocation of resources, especially man hours, is affected by the density. Due to the resource constraints, project managers are often forced to use overtime, which jeopardizes budget performance, or are forced to delay activities competing for the same resource, which results in delays in project completion times. Finally, a characteristic worth mentioning is the urgency of a project.

This is defined as the need to implement the project as soon as possible. In many cases project performance criteria are not met because of the urgency of a project. Projects which start after natural disasters are typical examples. In these situations, not enough time is allocated for planning and scheduling projects, and as a result projects are more likely to exceed budgets and be perceived as failures.

2.4.4. FACTORS RELATED TO PROJECT MANAGER AND TEAM MEMBERS

Project management action is a key for project success Hubbard 1990. Jaselskis and Ashley 1991 suggested that by using the management tools, the project managers would be able to plan and execute their construction projects to maximize the project's chances of success. Then, the variables in project management include adequate communication, control mechanisms, feedback capabilities, troubleshooting, coordination effectiveness, decision making effectiveness, monitoring, project organization structure, plan and schedule followed, and related previous management experience (Belout 1998; Chua et al. 1999; Walker and Vines 2000). A number of attributes will affect this factor, including the communication system, control mechanism, feedback capabilities, planning effort, organization structure, safety and quality assurance program, control of subcontractors' works, and finally the overall managerial actions. Many factors related to the skills and characteristics of project managers and team members are proposed for the successful completion of projects. In their recent study, Pinto and Slevin demonstrated the importance of selecting project managers who possess the necessary technical and administrative skills for successful project termination. They showed that the project manager's commitment and competence become most critical during the planning and termination stages.

The competence of the team members is also found to be a critical factor during the implementation stages.

Note that these factors not only affect project performance but they also have an impact on client satisfaction and project acceptance. For example, a project manager's marketing skills influence the client's attitude towards the project outcome. Similarly, well established communication channels between the project manager, the organization and the client are necessary for the acceptance of the project outcome by the client.

2.4.5. FACTORS RELATED TO ORGANIZATION

One of the most critical factors for the successful completion of projects is top management support. The support is usually strongest if there is a project champion and this champion is from the top management. He helps project managers understand and achieve the project objectives which are specified by the client and/or top management.

Top management usually controls a project manager's access to resources which are supervised by functional managers. The level of support provided by the functional manager is usually determined by the level of support from top management. If the project is part of the functional department, then the availability of resources is not usually an obstacle, because the functional manager is usually also the project manager. But for projects with matrix organizational forms, or for projects with pure project forms, acquiring adequate resources can be a difficult job. It requires negotiating skills and positional power within the organization. Clearly, full support from the organization for the project helps to facilitate and implement strategies for the successful completion of projects.

2.4.6. FACTORS RELATED TO EXTERNAL ENVIRONMENT

Various researchers support environment as a factor affecting the project success (Akinsola et al. 1997; Kaming et al. 1997; Songer and Molenaar 1997; Chua et al. 1999; Walker and Vines 2000 Akinsola et al.1997) further described environment as all external influences on the process, including social, political, and technical systems. The attributes used to measure this factor are economic environment, social environment, political environment, and level of technology advanced. This last group consists of factors which are external to the organization but still have an impact on project success or failure. A number of environmental factors, such as political, economic, and social, as well as factors related to the advances in technology or even factors related to nature affect project performance. In an empirical study by Pinto and Slevin, it was found that most of the environmental factors affect projects during the planning stage of a project's life-cycle. Yet some of the factors affect a project at all phases of the life-cycle, such as weather conditions and social environment.

Sometimes these factors are so influential that they cause a project to be terminated at the implementation stages.

In their book, Morris and Hough gave many illustrations of governments being influential external factors and showed how crucial the public attitude towards a project could become. Note that if a client is from outside the organization, the client should also be considered as an external factor influencing the project performance.

For functional projects, however, clients are usually part of the organization, such as top management. In such cases, factors related to the client can be grouped under the factors related to the organization. There might be additional external factors affecting project success, such as competitors in the market or subcontractors. They should also be listed with this group.

Any factor in this group might influence the availability of resources and thus the project manager's performance on the job. The subcontractors start their main duties when the project reaches the construction stage. The variables include contractor experience, site management, supervision and involvement of subcontracting, contractor's cash flow, effectiveness of cost control system, and speed of information flow (Chan and Kumaraswamy 1997; Dissanayaka and Kumaraswamy 1999.) The client-related factors concerned with client characteristics, client type and experience, knowledge of construction project organization, project financing, client confidence in the construction team, owner's construction sophistication, well-defined scope, owner's risk aversion, client project management. (Chan and Kumaraswamy 1997; Songer and Molenaar 1997; Dissanayaka and Kumaraswamy 1999).

Client consultation and acceptance are also influenced by the environmental factors. Similarly, the client might be the reason for ineffective consultation, which could lead to project failure. (Chan and Kumaraswamy 1997; Songer and Molenaar 1997; Dissanayaka and Kumaraswamy 1999).

2.4.7. FACTORS RELATED TO RISK, CULTURE AND PROCUREMENT PROCESS

Risk Failure to think ahead and to foresee and address potential problems (Classic mistake award winner) and Risk management is seen as an independent activity rather than an integral part of the planning process. Risk, problems and issues become confused as a result team isn't really doing risk management. Religion and culture The World Commission on Culture and Development defined culture as 'ways of living together' and argued that this made culture a core element of sustainable development. Almost all of the grave threats confronting human and planetary survival originate in human actions. However, much narrow thinking on sustainable development has focused almost exclusively on the relationships of people to the natural environment without considering the people-to-people relationships that lie at the core

of a sustainable society. Fulfilling today's human needs while preserving and protecting the natural environment for future generations requires equitable and harmonious interactions between individuals and communities. Developing cultural values that support these people-to-people and people-to-nature values has traditionally been the role of religion in most societies. Religion is a major influence in the world today. It seems that people in all cultures have a set of beliefs that go beyond both the self and the natural world. We use these beliefs to help explain reasons for human existence and to guide personal relationships and behavior. Part of the great diversity of humankind is the many different religions and belief systems we have developed Animism, Buddhism, Christianity, Hinduism, Islam, Jainism, Taoism, and many more. Religious beliefs have a strong influence on the culture of a community.

Indeed, for many people around the world, religious beliefs are central to their culture and provide the moral codes by which they live. Even where people in the contemporary world believe that the traditional beliefs of their parents and societies are not so relevant to their everyday lives, underlying religious beliefs about human worth and how to relate to other people and the Earth are still important parts of their lives. Many definitions of culture refer to particular values and beliefs. Other meanings refer to the everyday life and behavior of people that flow from these beliefs. Others are more general and refer to works of art. Culture is, therefore, an inextricable part of the complex notion of sustainability. It can be seen as an arbiter in the difficult trade-offs between conflicting ends with regard to development goals. As pointed out in the report of the World Commission on Culture and Development set up jointly by UNESCO and the United Nations, culture is not only the "servant of ends but the social basis of the ends themselves", a factor of development but also the "fountain of our progress and creativity". All these meanings or aspects of culture influence our worldviews and the ways in which we view our relationships with the Earth and each other. As a result, these aspects of culture affect different meanings of what it might mean to live sustainably. Culture is an important concept in projects for Sustainable Development. This is because the common cultural models in many societies often do not encourage sustainable development and what are needed are new, or rediscovered, norms and values that can guide our actions towards sustainable ways of caring for other people and the natural world.

2.5. EFFECT OF PROJECT SPECIFIC FACTOR ON THE FAILURE PROJECT

As stated by Alex S (2018) According to respondents' opinions, the survey's findings indicate that the analysis' top three project-specific related causes of project failure are as follows.

These include: - management issues, poor implementation, technical issues, market and marketing issues, the promoter's financial insolvency, poor worker quality, unmet objectives, and poor governance. The outcome of the document analysis report confirms that the three main project-specific related causes of project failure are management issues, market and marketing issues, and delays in project implementation. In-depth interviews with senior credit officers have also confirmed that problems with the market, the quality of the labor force, and implementation delays are what ultimately lead to a project's failure.

Arrow (1998), cited by Matu, (2020), in analyzing project failure factors for Kenya Railways projects, identified poor communication, little experience of the project manager late procurement of equipment, lack of training of project managers and slow project selection methods has been the major causes of project failure.

Role knowledge of project management, project implementation delay, which resulted from lack of adequate planning, delays in their lease of funds and frequent interference by policy makers, improper procurement process and planning without involvement of stakeholders are the factors for project failure in developing country *Yapetal (2021)*.

Maina, (2018), identified that 32 possible causes of Ghanaian government project failure among these factors poor monitoring, political interference, fluctuation of prices management practices, procurement processes, project funding, commitment to project, selection of project managers, project management techniques and scope change are determinants of project failure. Poor financial capacity, inaccurate costing and corruption, incompetence and lack of knowledge, poor planning and estimation, poor communication, poor contracting and contractor practices and frequent design scope changes are causes for project failure in developing country Zahran, et al (2023).

Vicente et al., (2018) cited by Laguna, (2022), the field of project management, complexity is closely related to project outcomes that determine project success and failure factors. As per his study the prevalent order that influence the success of project are project factors, organization related factors, project manager and team members factors and external factors. These are management problem, poor implementation, technical failure, market and marketing problem, financial insolvency of the promoter, quality of man power failure, missing objectives and poor governance.

The document analysis report result also confirms that management problem, market and marketing problems and delay in project implementation are the major project specific related cause of project failure, TEFERI, (2020).

2.6. ROLE OF CREDIT MANAGEMENT RELATED CAUSES OF PROJECT FAILURE

According to TEFERI, (2020), Taking into account the opinion of the respondents, the result of the survey shows that the reasons for project failures related to credit management are divided according to the agreement of the respondents as follows: the level of monitoring or technical consultation, the evaluation of projects at the current price, overestimation of project returns and lenders' ability to plan the project are the main reasons for project failure. The results of the document analysis report also show that the lenders did not perform a rigorous follow-up on the financed projects and the bank performs poor credit analysis, such as insufficient market and project feasibility studies by the bank.

The review overestimated the project's cash flow or revenue and the absence of reliable prices, markets and costs production data for project planning purposes. In addition, due to factors related to credit management, Poor tracking function or activities in banking consultations provided by the bank, incorrect credit assessment(analysis) performed by the bank is supported by the defendant as if this could cause the project to fail.

According to Alex (2018) According to respondents' opinions, the survey's findings indicate that the following causes of project failure are ranked in order of respondents' agreement: Major factors that contribute to a project failing include lack of follow-up or technical support, project appraisals using current prices, overestimations of return on investment, and the financiers' capacity for project planning.

The document analysis report's findings also point to the credit performers' lack of strict oversight of financed projects, the bank's poor credit analysis (such as its lack of a proper market and project viability study), the overestimation of the project's cash flow or revenue during appraisal, and the lack of trust worthy price, market, and cost of production data for project planning purposes. Moreover, from aspects of credit management the interviewee supports the bank's improper credit appraisal (analysis) and poor follow-up functions or activities as factors that can contribute to a project's failure.

Yilkal (2015). When the weighted average recruitment variation of the project's man-power in terms of number, qualification and experience are increased by 1% from below the plan that is stated in the Banks appraisal document project failure will be increased by 10.7%.

Whenever the estimation of cash flow of a project is overstated by 1% from what the project is, actually generating project failure will be increased by 6.6%.

Patrick (2015) the government of Malawi, in 2001, through the then Ministry of Irrigation and Water Development secured funding amounting to UA9.67 million from African Development Bank (ADB) to implement the Horticulture and Food Crops Development Project. However, the HFCDP did not meet its aims and objectives and is a typical example of big projects that have failed in the agriculture sector. His study identified that that involve right people with appropriate expertise, promote ownership, adopt bottom-up approach and assess contractors are important for project success. In addition, proper project monitoring, execution of situational assessment, need to undertake a comprehensive needs assessment, strengthen cooperatives and establishing linkages of the project beneficiaries to markets where they can sell their produce can reduce project failure.

Alex (2018) has also conducted research to identify Causes of Failure of Projects financed by Development Bank of Ethiopia, the Case of Dessie District. As per his finding management problem, market and marketing problems and delay in project implementation are the major project specific related cause of project failure. From the credit management factors follow-up level, appraisals of project using current price, over estimation of return from project and project planning capacity of the financiers are major causes a project to fail.

2.7. EFFECT OF MACRO ECONOMICAL RELATED CAUSES OF PROJECT FAILURE

According to TEFERI, (2020), Continuous price increases for goods, raw materials, and wages, as well as in-depth interviews and surveys, strongly support sudden changes in economic policies. Similar to recruitment variation, the coefficient of sales short fall depicts that the existence of significant positive relation with failure of DBE financed projects at 10% precession level. According to the value of marginal effect, the probability of project failure is increasing by 31% when the product sales decreases by 1% from the appraisal report. The odd ratio has depicted that the probability of the project being failed to successful is 1.34 to 1 if the projects product sales decreases by 1% from appraisal report sales estimations. This simply shows that product-marketing problem is the one among the major cause of failure for DBE financed projects. (AdamuL,2013).

According to Alex S (2018), Continuous rise of product price, raw materials price and wages, sudden change in economic policies, the problems of corruption and related problems and intervention of political leaders or government official's perception towards the project are among the major factors for project failure.

2.8. EFFECT OF SOCIO-POLITICAL RELATED CAUSES OF PROJECT

FAILURE

While government official's perception of the project has only received support from survey results, Alex S (2018), the problems of corruption and related problems, as well as the intervention of political leaders on the project, have all received support from both Ado, & Choudhury, (2012), The project size, clarity of objectives, the proportion of funding from abroad, and political conditions have significant effects on the rate of implementation of externally assisted development projects in Africa. An increase in project size by \$1 million will lead to a 0.04 decrease in the implementation rate of projects. Yilkal (2015).

When the weighted average recruitment variation of the project's work force in terms of number, qualification and experience are increased by 1% from below the plan that is stated in the Banks appraisal document project failure will be increased by 10.7%.

Whenever the estimation of cash Alex (2018) flow of a project is over stated by 1% from what the project is, actually generating project failure will be increased by 6.6%. As I have gathered from different project follow up reports of the bank in addition to the above-discussed literatures, the occurrence of COVID-19 has big impact on project performance for both under implementation and operational projects. According to TEFERI, (2020), the problems related to corruption and related issues and the participation of political leaders in the project was confirmed by both survey results and interviews, while the public officials' opinion about the project was confirmed only by the survey results.

2.9. LITERATURE GAP

For cases for project, failure different researches had conducted. Patrick (2015) has conducted research to assess the factors of Horticulture and Food Crops Development Project failure in The Central Region of Malawi. However, the current study will determine in Ethiopia, which has location gap. Alex S (2018) has also conducted with the same title with the current study, but restricted only for projects financed by Development Bank of Ethiopia, Dessie district. The major factors of failure for Development Bank of Ethiopia financed projects identified by Adamu Legese (2013) research showed that, some project specific explanatory variables, such as marketing problem and human resource recruitment variation in aggravating project failure, but project implementation time overrun to decrease project failure.

Moreover, development bank of Ethiopia's project planning capacity and exchange rate change are found statistically significant in increasing project failure from development bank of Ethiopia's credit management and macro-economic explanatory variables respectively.

Among sociopolitical variables, population size and literacy level in which the projects are working are found to be statistically significant in decreasing project failure as both variables increasing. However, the current study has time frame gap of 8 years. The study has conducted for failure factors only for projects started operation. However, this study cases for project failures to identify the factors of project failure at both under implementation stage and already start operation financed by the Development Bank of Ethiopia from 2017 to 2021. In general, even tough, there are different researches and recommendations on project failure the Development Bank of Ethiopia financed project NPL, ration is not as per the acceptable range. This indicates the failure of financed projects and need of further research.

2.10. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

As indicated in the above theories and empirics different factors affect the project failure. These factors arise from internal or external part of the project; which means there may be arises from the client, who pays for the project and a result benefit from its deliverables. In case of DBE, the factor for project failure arises from the Bank side, which covers partial investment cost of the project but not directly use the project output or benefit, from the client side, which is the main beneficiary of the project, and from external variables, which are beyond the control of both sides. Thus, identifying the variables, which are significantly variables failure, is important to mitigate failure factors.

The researcher has selected the following variables in order to analyze whether they have significant causes for project failure. With regard to the relationship between these four categories of independent variables and the dependent variable, it is believed that when projects have good strength not be failed easily. From the banks credit management practices good appraisal, on time fund release and proper project follow up protect projects failure. The macro-economic factors devaluation of local money and inflation aggravate project failure. On the other hand, the socio-political environment, social unrest and occurrence of corona virus pandemic in tends for project failure. Based on these beliefs, the under listed four hypotheses are generated:

- ❖ The project specific factors project implementation delay, management problems and quality of products and marketing problems have no significant impact for project failure in the case of Development Bank of Ethiopia financed projects.
- ❖ From Bank's credit management practice good appraisal, on time fund release and proper project follow up are not significant factors of projects failure in the case of Development Bank of Ethiopia financed projects.
- ❖ From Socio- political environment and social unrest and occurrence of Corona virus

pandemic have no significant impact for project failure in the case of Development Bank of Ethiopia financed projects.

FIGURE 2.1 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORKS

Source: adapted (Adamu legese,2013)

CHAPTER THREE

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. INTRODUCTION

This part of the study focused on the methods, which refer to the procedural framework of the research conducted. Moreover, the chapter presents research methodology, population, sample size, research design and other related issues.

3.2. DESCRIPTION OF THE STUDY AREA

The current study focused on factors affecting for projects failure, which are financed by Development Bank of Ethiopia. Specifically focus on the failed projects financed by Development Bank of Ethiopia head office. Development bank of Ethiopia head office-located at Kirkos Addis Ababa Sub cite. Nearest banks, Commercial ODA TOWER, 200 m. Zemen Bank, 273m. Commercial Bank of Ethiopia 'Kazanchis' Branch, 636m. Wegagen Bank,746 m. Abay Bank S.co, 770 m. Enat Bank SC Head Office, 840 m.

3.3. RESEARCH DESIGN AND RESEARCH APPROACH

3.3.1. RESEARCH DESIGN

As we know, research design is the plan (to get relevant information). It is a strategy (to collect and analyze data) and it is budget (to show cost and time constraint). This study had presented an empirical analysis of important assessment the causes for project failure, which the case development bank of Ethiopia. To achieve this objective descriptive and explanatory research design are adopted in the study. The explanatory type of research design helps to identify and evaluate the causal relationships between the different variables under consideration Marczyk et al, (2005). Explanatory research determines the relationship between dependent variable (failure of projects) within dependent variables. The study also explained the results by comparing with empirical evidences. Hypotheses will be formulated and test based on empirical reviews on similar subject matter. For this study, the researcher used both descriptive and explanatory research design. Descriptive statistics utilized to describe like table, mean and percentage. While Explanatory analysis conducted by using multiple regression models to analyze cause-effect relation between factors affecting of project failure and the case of Development Bank of Ethiopia projects.

3.3.2. RESEARCH APPROACH

There are two basic approaches to research, quantitative and qualitative approach. In this study both qualitative and quantitative approach was adopted to do effective study. Quantitative methods are fairly inflexible; the advantage of this inflexibility is that it allows for meaningful comparison of responses across participants and study sites. Quantitative approach were used to analyze the performance of the assesses causes project failure the study area by quantifying the results obtained from data collection through statistical summary and analysis.

Qualitative research relies on the collection of qualitative data (i.e., non-numerical data such as words and pictures). The main focus in qualitative research is to understand, explain, explore, discover and clarify situations, feelings, perceptions, attitudes, values, beliefs and experiences of a group of people (Qualitative research approach was used to analyze the second objective of the study, which is to assess internal validity, clarity and comprehensiveness of the assessment causes the project failure in case of development bank of Ethiopia to complement the findings of the quantitative approach. It was appropriate to study the selected issues in-depth and which includes survey questionnaires and structured interview. Kumar,(2011]. So that for this study the researcher used qualitative approach.

In addition, to test the null hypothesis formulated under chapter two above. Multiple liner regression is use to model the relationship between dichotomous dependent variable and multiple independent variables. In order to assess the major factors of project failure the researcher applied both qualitative and quantitative approaches. Based on the purpose of the study and the nature of the research question aiming to provide a better understanding the researcher applied both qualitative and quantitative approach.

3.4. TYPE AND SOURCE OF DATA

Information will be gathered from different sources; these was from primary and secondary. The researcher was employing both primary and secondary data sources was used to substantiate the findings of the study.

3.4.1. PRIMARY SOURCE

Primary data was gathering through questionnaire for targeted officers in the select projects and promoter's /customer/ of the Bank. Primary data sources include information obtained from respondents by dispatching both response questionnaires, and conducting interviews.

3.4.2. SECONDARY SOURCE

Secondary data sources were manual of human resource management's report and organization performance of the internet statistical reports in the bank's report.

In addition, secondary data was collected from customer files (Follow-ups) and the bank's report. Secondary data may be acquired from various sources: Reports of various kinds, books, periodicals, reference books (encyclopedia), university publications (thesis, dissertations, etc.), policy documents, statistical compilations, proceedings, personal documents (historical studies), The Internet etc.

3.5. METHODS OF DATA COLLECTION

3.5.1. QUESTIONNAIRE

A series of questions that are easy and convenient to answer but can describe the intended practices or behaviors was formulated into a questionnaire. Shao (1999) defines a questionnaire as a formal set of questions or statements designed to gather information from respondents that accomplish research objectives. For the research primary data was collected via questionnaire and observations in, 50 % of the Primary data was collected through questionnaire from targeted officers and managers in the bank, while the remaining 50% to be collected from the selected failed projects management staff and owners of the projects. Questionnaire and annual report of the development bank of Ethiopia analysis was the main data collecting tools for this studying. This respect the questionnaire will be answered by the employees in the project. The available options from which they have to select may not be exhaustive to describe the situation of the respondent. The questionnaire may be disseminated to the respondents in different ways as shown below:

- a) Deliver and drop and pick up after respondents have responded
- b) It was administered face to face.

3.5.2. INTERVIEWS

Interview as opposed to questionnaire requires more in depth answers and takes longer and more resources to carry out. It requires setting up appointments at the convenience of both the researcher and the respondents and it takes a longer period of time to get as much information as you could get from a questionnaire (Shao, 1999). The questions of the interview as with the questionnaire may be structured; the interview takes placed face to face.

3.6. SAMPLE DESIGN

3.6.1. POPULATION OF THE STUDY

Development Bank of Ethiopia's core function is financing medium- and long-term priority area development projects. The populations (projects) for this study were manufacturing commercial agriculture and mining sectors financed from at head; office (corporate level) financed projects due to time and cost constraints. The unit of analysis for this research is for projects financed at head office only. The target population for the study was projects financed by Development Bank of Ethiopia from 2018-2023 at head office.

3.6.2. SAMPLE SIZE DETERMINATION AND SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

Sampling frame for the target population of the study was all projects financed by Development Bank of Ethiopia from 2018-2023 at head office. Since the number of targeted populations is 96. To have fruitful finding the researcher used census-sampling techniques. Among those total 96 projects, there searcher collected the data by using judgmental sampling technique, which allows their searcher to used judgmental sampling. As result for the primary data, which collect by questionnaire, the researcher selects 48 samples from the project's staff and 42 from the bank's staffs and also 6 from top management selected for interviews from the target population. Hence, due to this low lending limit of districts, more than 80% of the total loan portfolio of the Bank is found in Head Office.

Accordingly, a study the populations (projects) was select by purposive sampling only from head office (corporate level) based on loan sanctioning limit from above 45 million. Types of respondents, population size, Sample size, Sampling technique and Tools of Data Collection.

TABLE 3.1 RESPONDENTS OF DATA COLLECTION

No	Respondents	Population size	Sample Size	Sampling Technique		Tools of data collection
				Project failure	Respondent	
1	From the project failure Staff and project owner	42	42	Census	Judgmental	Questionnaire
2	From top management	6	6	Census	Judgmental	Interview
3	From the bank's credit staff	48	48	Census	Judgmental	Questionnaire
	Total	96	96	-	-	-

3.7. RELIABILITY AND VALIDITY

While developing the questionnaire, two conditions are considered; validity and reliability. Cronbach's alpha coefficient, there searcher used it to investigate their liability of the questionnaires. Validity refers to how accurately a method measures what it is intended to measure. If research has, high validity that means it produces results that correspond to real properties, characteristics, and variations in the physical or social world (Middle ton.f).

TABLE3.2. RELIABILITY TEST RESULT SOURCE: SPSS OUTPUT.

No	Factors	Number of Items	Cranach's Alpha result
1	Project Specific factors	15	.903
2	Bank's Credit Management Factors	17	.950
4	Socio-political Environment Factors	9	.678
Total		46	.843

In the study, the Cranach's alpha coefficient was calculated for each field of the questionnaire. Table3.2 above shows the values of Cronbach's alpha for the entire questionnaire. Questionnaires are prepared in a way that is closely related to research question and appropriate and careful data collection method was used. Cronbach's Alpha test of reliability is in social science studies is important (Taber, 2018) cited by Haidari, et al (2021), An Alpha value of less than 0.6, as suggested by the author and used by some other studies, is not considered reliable. All factors were reasonably reliable as the Cronbach's Alpha's coefficients were above the threshold value of 0.70, which is a 0. 843. Therefore, it can be said that the above questionnaires were adequately reliable.

3.8. DATA PROCESSING AND ANALYSIS

The collected data is checked, sorted and analyzed regarding to the objective of the study. Finally, the data was processed and analyzed by statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 26. In addition, the researcher used descriptive analysis technique, which used to describe each variable (Kothari, 2004). Numerical data collected from questionnaire of the study were analyzed by using frequency, percentage and mean score in table. Analysis refers to the computation of certain measures a long with searching for patterns of relationship that exist among data-groups.

Thus, in the process of analysis, relationships or differences supporting or conflicting with original or new hypotheses was subjected to statistical tests of significance to determine with what validity data can be said to point out any conclusions. Which is performer with the purpose of summarizing the collect table data and organizing these in such a manner that they answer the research questions.

3.8.1. DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

The SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) software was utilized to scrutinize the answers obtained from the survey. All the data and details collected through the survey were encoded and inputted in to the SPSS program to derive variable frequency, percentage, mean, Grand mean, and standard deviation. After that, the data was prepared for supplementary analysis through factor analysis, statistical tests, and descriptive analysis.

3.8.2. INFERENCE STATISTICS

Inferential statistics used to test probability theory and hypotheses, permit inferences from a sample to a population for this purpose, the study was used coloration and regression analysis in general and Pearson correlation and multiple regression in particular to detect the association between scores on the research variables. Furthermore, in this study, all the data was processed by using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26. To do it so, inferential statistics specifically correlation (Pearson correlation analysis) and regression model (multiple regression model are mandatory tools of analysis and used to generalize beyond the data. However, qualitative method of analyzing is stand for analyzing qualitative information and to do it so, descriptive statistics is employed. According to Cochran, (1977) cited by Tong, (2019). Descriptive statistics as part of statistics deal with methods of organizing, summarizing, arranging and reporting data without generalization beyond the data. Because of the above afore mentioned reasons, the researcher was employing both qualitative and quantitative methods of data analysis integrated to inferential statistics and descriptive statistics respectively. In this research, the major variables were study and their findings was present or displayed in the form of tables and figures. This was depended up on the nature of the data, the type of data, and the method and design employed as well as findings.

3.9. MODEL SPECIFICATION

According to Marsh, et al, (2014), model construction involves specifying relationships between two or more variables; perhaps extending to the development of descriptive or exploratory equations. In order to achieve the objectives of this study, multiple linear regression models are used.

Multiple linear regression is a regression method that estimates the relationship between quantitative dependent variable and two or more independent variables. The dependent variable is ordering response continuous variable and independent variable may be categorical or continuous. Linear regression turns up often in the social, for example in the modeling of human levels of preference (on scale from, say, 1-5 for very poor through excellent) as well as in information retrieval.

Moreover, it is computed by the following formula. $Y = B_0 + B_1 X_1 + B_2 X_2 + B_p X_p$ Where, B_0 = the intercept, $B_1 - B_p$ = Regression coefficients, $X_1 - X_{up}$ = independent variables $Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + e$ Y = project failure X_1 = project specific factor. X_2 = Bank's credit management factor, X_3 : Socio-political environment factor β_0 = Constant $\beta_1 - \beta_4$ = Regression co-efficient and; e = error term.

3.10. ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

Ethical Considerations can be specified as one of the most important parts of the research. Dissertations may even be doomed to failure if this part is missing. In order to address ethical considerations aspect of my dissertation in an effective manner, the study would need to expand discussions according to each of the following points. The research purpose was clearly introduced for all participants of this study. Concerning the right of privacy of the respondents, the study assured the confidentiality of the identity of each participant. There was voluntary participation of respondents in the research was important. The use of offensive, discriminatory, or other unacceptable language needs to be avoided in the formulation of Questionnaire/Interview. Privacy and anonymity of respondents were of a paramount importance.

CHAPTER FOUR

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1. INTRODUCTION

The chapter bargains with introduction and discussion of the factual result of both the expressive and inferential measurements/statistics Appropriately, expressive statistics employs the information to provide descriptions of the population, either through numerical calculations or charts or tables. Inferential measurements make deductions and forecasts almost a population based on a sample of data taken from the population in question. In addition, descriptive statistics stand for the change of raw data into valuable data, which can be interpreted to clarify a group of dimensions. This shape/form of measurable investigation can incorporate a number of yields, counting frequencies, percentage, implies and standard deviation. Inferential statistics could be a portion of statistics that's concerned with the examination, interpretation and drawing conclusion approximately the data. The taking after clear demographic comes about are displayed to indicate the collected information were picked up from the individual body, who have great understanding and experienced for the dispersed questionnaire in common/general, but no the part of examination to reply the research targets.

4.2. RESPONSE RATE

For this consider 96 questionnaires/survey were utilized/used to collected data from client of the bank and the credit performer of the bank. The table 4.1, underneath demonstrates the reaction rate of the questionnaires: -

TABLE: 4.1, RESPONSE RATE

Result	Frequency	Percentage
Responded	90	94%
Not responded	6	6%
Total	96	100%

Source: own survey SPSS output

As appeared/showed within the Table 4.1, over a total of 96 surveys/questionnaires were conveyed/distributed to the client of the bank and the credit entertainer of the bank. Out of the overall dispatched questionnaires, 90(94%) were filled up and returned and 6 respondents were remained without returned the inquired questionnaires.

This appears/show that, the reaction rate is around 94%, which is at acceptable rate concurring/according to Sheehan, (2001).

TABLE 4.2: GENDER OF RESPONDENTS

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	39	40.6	44.3	44.3
	Female	49	51.0	55.7	100.0
	Total	88	91.7	100.0	
Missing	11	8	8.3		
Total		96	100.0		

Source: Survey data (2024)

This study endeavored to determine the sex distribution of respondents. Respondents to this study were anticipated to be male and female workers of Project Administration and the Development Bank of Ethiopia. Subsequently, as portion of the study, respondents were inquired to reveal their sexual orientation by checking the suitable box on the questionnaire. The overview found that 40.6 percent of representatives taking part within the overview were male and 51.0 percent were female, and 8.3 respondents were remained without returned and lost the inquired surveys. According to the information, the overviewed companies employed both male and female workers. Information recommend that suppositions communicated are gender-specific.

TABLE 4.3: EDUCATION LEVEL OF RESPONDENTS

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Diploma	7	7.3	8.0	8.0
	BA or BSc	51	53.1	58.0	65.9
	MA/MSc	22	22.9	25.0	90.9
	PhD	8	8.3	9.1	100.0
	Total	88	91.7	100.0	
Missing	11	8	8.3		
Total		96	100.0		

Source: own survey SPSS output.2024

With respect to educational level, most of the respondents have to begin with degree holders. As can be seen within the table 4.3, over, almost 7.3% of the respondents have Diploma, 58.1% of the respondents are degree holders and 22.9% are Masters Holders.

As we have seen from over table the lion's share of the respondent's degree and Masters Holder, in expansion there were 9.1 Ph.D. holders and 8 respondents were remained without returned and missing/lost the inquired questionnaires. This appears that the respondents are competent and reliable to investigate the supporting issues related to the study and can get it and discharge their order within the administration of projects.

TABLE 4.4: AGE OF RESPONDENTS

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	20-25 years	21	21.9	23.9	23.9
	26-35 years	25	26.0	28.4	52.3
	36-45 years	21	21.9	23.9	76.1
	above 46 years	21	21.9	23.9	100.0
	Total	88	91.7	100.0	
Missing	11	8	8.3		
Total		96	100.0		

Source: SPSS output 2024

Table 4.4 shows that 21.9 % from 20-25 a long time/year 26.0% from 26-35 a long time 21.9% from 36-45 a long time 21.9ove 49 a long-time respondent. Thus, these respondents spoken to the over normal of the focused-on individuals of the study population who were inside the youthful age groups of the individuals who were evidently important instruments for affecting change.

TABLE 4.5: TYPES OF THE PROJECT

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Manufacturing	22	22.9	25.0	25.0
	Agriculture	27	28.1	30.7	55.7
	Mining	28	29.2	31.8	87.5
	Service	11	11.5	12.5	100.0
	Total	88	91.7	100.0	
Missing	11	8	8.3		
Total		96	100.0		

Source: SPSS output 2024

As shown in the above table 4.5, about 76.1 percent of the targeted population for the study is under the manufacturing sector, 22 percent from agriculture sector and 27 percent from mining sector 29.2 percent another 11.5 percent and 8 respondents were remained and missing without returned the asked questionnaires.

TABLE 4.6: FORM OF COMPANIES

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	sole proprietorship	17	17.7	19.3	19.3
	Plc	36	37.5	40.9	60.2
	Corporation	35	36.5	39.8	100.0
	Total	88	91.7	100.0	
Missing	11	8	8.3		
Total		96	100.0		

Source: SPSS output 2024

As shown in the above table from the total targeted population were from followed by sole proprietorship 17.7% and 37.5 % from PLC and corporation is only 36.5% of the sample companies and 8 respondents were remained without missing returned the asked questionnaires.

TABLE 4.7: CURRENT POSITION OF RESPONDENTS IN THE PROJECT/BANK

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	General manager	6	6.3	6.8	6.8
	Team manager	6	6.3	6.8	13.6
	Project manager	11	11.5	12.5	26.1
	Loan officer	20	20.8	22.7	48.9
	Senior loan officer	18	18.8	20.5	69.3
	Senior expert	17	17.7	19.3	88.6
	Junior expert	10	10.4	11.4	100.0
	Total	88	91.7	100.0	
Missing	11	8	8.3		
Total		96	100.0		

Source: own survey SPSS output 2024

The position of respondents has moreover over the top impact/effect on the unwavering quality of the information and it has noteworthy commitments in giving the solid and substantial/valid data for this study. As delineated within the over table 4.7, most of respondents are Credit officer and Senior loan officer. The two positions together accounted an aggregate rate of (38.8%). This appears that the data was filled by more experienced and concerned body. 17.7% and 10.4%, extra 24.8% general supervisor, group manager and project supervisor of the respondent are moreover senior loan officers and project Directors separately and 5 respondents were remained without returned and lost the inquired questionnaires.

TABLE 4.8: RESPONDENT RELIGIOUS

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Orthodox	26	27.1	29.5	29.5
	Catholic	8	8.3	9.1	38.6
	Protestant	19	19.8	21.6	60.2
	Muslim	25	26.0	28.4	88.6
	Other	10	10.4	11.4	100.0
	Total	88	91.7	100.0	
Missing	11	8	8.3		
Total		96	100.0		

Source: own survey SPSS output 2024

With respect to respondents religious, most of the respondents have to begin with orthodox. As can be seen within the table 4.8, over, around 27.1% of the respondents have orthodox, 8.3% of the respondents are catholic, 29.2% are anther 19.8% protestant 26.0% Muslim and also 10.4% other. As we have seen from over table the larger part of the respondent's Muslim and orthodox, additionally 8 respondents were remained without returned and lost the inquired questionnaires. This appears that the respondents are competent and reliable to investigate the supporting issues related to the think about and can get it and release their mandate within the administration of projects.

TABLE 4.9: RESPONDENT MARTIAL STATUTES

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Single	22	22.9	25.0	25.0
	Married	56	58.3	63.6	88.6
	Window	10	10.4	11.4	100.0
	Total	88	91.7	100.0	
Missing	11	8	8.3		
Total		96	100.0		

Source: SPSS output 2024

As shown in the above table from the total targeted population 22.9% were from Single followed by married 58.3% and window is only 10.5% of the sample companies and 8 respondents were remained without missing returned the asked questionnaires.

TABLE 4.10: THE PARTICIPANTS WORK EXPERIENCE IN THE INDUSTRY

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Less than 2 years	9	9.4	10.2	10.2
	2-3 years	39	40.6	44.3	54.5
	4-6 years	16	16.7	18.2	72.7
	More than 6 years	24	25.0	27.3	100.0
	Total	88	91.7	100.0	
Missing	11	8	8.3		
Total		96	100.0		

Source: SPSS output 2024

Therefore, the probability of getting reliable information is very high as most of the respondents are experienced experts in the industry.

Source: SPSS output 2024

FIGURE 4.1: WORK EXPERIENCE IN THE INDUSTRY

4.3. CAUSES FOR PROJECT FAILURE THE CAUSES OF DEVELOPMENT BANK OF ETHIOPIA FINANCED PROJECTS,

Provide the mean and standard deviation of the reactions to the 46 things on the Multifactor project disappointment questionnaire scale with respect to the respondents' impressions of the particular extend disappointment, bank credit administration macro-economic factor, and socio-political figure factors. All factors have comparative/similar standard deviations, showing an agreement of reactions as the average reactions are equitably spread over all tried factors.

Descriptive statistics include creating particular lists from raw data, such as cruel scores, standard deviations, and rates for each subgroup, as clarified by Pallant (2005).

Interpreting these values can demonstrate the level of effectiveness in preventing extortion. Making break even with intervals for a run of five focuses on a Likert scale (extending from exceptionally high to very low) is suggested for analyzing information, and standard deviation is the favored estimation. Little standard deviations demonstrate information is near to the cruel, whereas an expansive standard deviation (compared to the mean) demonstrates information focuses are removed from the mean, making the mean a poor fit for the information. The variables were measured employing a five-point Likert scale where 1 speaks to exceptionally low and 5 speaks to exceptionally tall. Hence, the interpretation of the mean of each variable falls between the two ranges, and in the event that the mean approaches 1, the respondents have a very low impression of the variable, whereas a mean approaching 5 demonstrates the inverse, as expressed by Ghosh et al, (2013). To causes the minimum and most extreme length of a 5-point Likert sort scale, assist data is required.

TABLE 4.11: DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS 5-POINT LIKERT TYPE SCALE,

Scale	Interpretation
1 to 1.80	Represent (very Low)
1.81 until 2.60	Represent(low)
2.61 until 3.40	Represent(medium)
3.41 until 4.20	Represent (high)
4.21 until 5.00	Represent (very high)

Source: SPSS output 2024

4.4. DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS PROJECT SPECIFIC FACTOR

TABLE 4.12: PROJECT SPECIFIC FACTOR.

Project implementation problems	Mean	St. Deviation
	4.0928	0.48598
Experience or exposure to implement the project	4.148	.6872
Procurement Knowledge gap	4.0682	.65733
Risk Assessment Skill limitation	4.136	.5505
Decision making ability	4.0795	.64721
Resource Management Skill	4.0341	.63334
Communication skill	4.0909	.58006
Management Problem	4.0682	0.42502
Hiring Relatives	4.0682	.60259
Experience of Management staff	4.0227	.58678
Educational Qualification	4.0909	.59955
Leadership problem	4.0909	.55989
Quality of products and marketing problem	4.0750	0.49846
Absence of Quality control	3.9773	.54619
Use of obsolete technology	4.0909	.63674
Unavailability of quality raw material	4.1023	.60723
Stiff market competition	4.1136	.71810
No bargaining power in the international market	4.0909	.70526
Grand Mean	4.0803	

Source: own survey SPSS output 2024

Table 4.12: Descriptive analysis regarding to project specific factors

As delineated/depicted within the over table 4.12, the normal value of mean all It appears that it has 15 questions in three measurements, with answers extending from Project execution/implementation issues/problems Mean=4.0928(S. D = 0.48598). Administration Problem Mean=4.0682(S-D= 0.42502). Quality of item and marketing issue Mean=4.0750(S-D=0.49846). Respondents are development bank of Ethiopia and project staff work force who replied questions on a scale of 1 to 5. All extend particular calculate has a normal cruel score of (Mean =, 4.0803 S. D =0.84387).

This least model is surpassed by the mean rating extend/project particular figure Mean=4.0682. said explanations is higher more noteworthy than 4, showing that project-specific variables like issues with extend usage, managerial issues, and item quality and promoting issues enormously impact the sustainability of projects within the industry.

The success of project implementation is intensely impacted by different variables, such as the experience or introduction of the group, information holes in procurement, decision-making capacities, asset administration skills, and communication aptitudes of supervisors. Administrative issues just like the experience of supervisors, their educational capabilities, and hiring strategies can moreover contribute to project disappointment/failure. Moreover, the quality of items and marketing procedures, including the nonappearance of quality control, the utilize of outdated technology, the inaccessibility of raw materials, solid showcase competition, and a need of haggling control, can lead to project disappointment. In creating nations, poor monetary capacity, wrong cost estimation and debasement, incompetence and need of information, destitute arranging and estimation, destitute communication, poor contracting and contractor hones, and visit plan scope changes are the major causes of project disappointment (Lord & MANU, 2019).

Over estimation of cash stream amid project examination can moreover essentially affect project disappointment, especially for projects financed by the Development Bank of Ethiopia, as expressed by (Teferi, 2020). In terms of project-specific components, administration problems, poor usage, market and promoting issues, and disappointments within the quality of labor are the major causes of project disappointment/failure.

The report investigation of the credit recuperation report moreover states that the promoter's administration issues, counting need of information and experience in overseeing bank financing, issues with the market and marketing, deficiencies and cost vacillations of raw materials, and delays in actualizing ventures like development for working advance and the buy of machinery and in raising equity commitment in accordance with the agreement, are the most projects.

Generally, the grand mean of the project specific factor is **4.08**. this implies that most of the respondents are high on the issue that project specific factor like managerial problem, projects implementation problems and quality of products and marketing strategy is the main Cause for project failures in the sampled companies.

4.5. DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS BANK'S CREDIT MANAGEMENT FACTORS

TABLE 4.13: DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF BANK'S CREDIT MANAGEMENT FACTORS

Appraisal's problem	Mean	Std. Deviation
	4.1307	.50694
Over/ under appraisal	4.3523	.74340
Appraising project with current price only	4.1705	.68181
Missing of investment items	4.0682	.62137
Short implementation schedule	4.0909	.67187
Lack of contingency planning	4.0682	.67459
Use of unreal data	4.0795	.68181
Problem of fund release	4.1273	.49752
Equity blocking problem	4.2273	.73855
Unable to fulfill terms and conditions	4.2045	.69744
Long process of fund release	4.0114	.55697
Capacity of credit performers	4.1136	.59561
Unethical act of credit performer	4.0795	.64721
Follow-up	4.0947	.50464
Not conduct follow up as per the plan	4.0795	.64721
Data validation problem	4.1250	.62169
Risk identification problem during follow up	4.0455	.72570
Capacity problem of follow up performer	4.0455	.60475
Limitation to provide technical advice	4.0455	.60475
No action as per the follow-up Recommendation	4.0341	.59594
Grand Mean	4.10823	0.50303

Source: own survey SPSS output 2024

As appeared within the over table 4.13, the mean value of It shows that it has 17 questions in three measurements, with answers extending from Appraisal's issue Mean=4.1307 (S. D = 0.50694). Problem of fund discharge Mean=4.1273 (S-D= 0.49752). Follow-up Mean=4.0947 (S-D=0.50464). Respondents are development bank of Ethiopia and project administration staff work force who replied questions on a scale of 1 to 5.

All factors are more than 4.01. Which appears that the respondents are high on the expressed thought. The banks credit administration process affects the projects execution within the industry, examination issue, problem of finance release, and follow-up issues are the fundamental factors for project disappointment. Beneath/ over evaluation, apprise with current price, use of unreal information, lack of contingency arranging is watched issues within the examination issue with average approximated mean value 4.11.

Problem of finance release like value blocking issues, incapable to fulfill term and conditions, long issue of finance discharge, unethical act of credit performer is the Cause for the project disappointment within the sampled projects. Credit management-related variables have been the subject of record examination, and it has been reported that frail credit investigation by the bank, such as need of strict follow-up of financed ventures by the credit entertainers, and the most reasons why a project with bank financing comes up short include insufficient market and project viability examination by the bank, thinking little of cash stream/flow or revenue from the extend amid evaluation, and a need of solid cost, market, and cost of generation information for project arranging. In expansion, need of legitimate follow-up is the other Cause for project failure. From the macro-economic components accessibility of outside money and steady trade rate are very essential. For imported investment things the bank distribute budget with the current date or at the announcing date of evaluation, not as it were imported things but moreover installments for remote specialists arranged by the rate at the reporting date. In any case, the accessibility of foreign currency exceptionally restricted and the trade rate profoundly expanded from time to time.

As per the secondary information collected from the project take after up reports of development bank of Ethiopia financed projects deficiency of remote cash and trade rate increase, ventures not executed and worked as per the arrange and entered in to fizzled extend self-control. In any case, as appeared within the over table 4.13 macro-economic variables are measurably noteworthy since its particular cruel is around 4. The result isn't reliable with the finding of (Alex S, 2018). It has been concluded that the ensuing components relating to bank or credit administration are significant reasons for the disappointment of a venture: lacking checking or direction, assessing project recommendations based on display esteem rather than future value, and inadequacy of agents to arrange ventures. These components are mindful for the destruction of a extend that has been financed (Teferi, 2020).

For the most part, the grand mean for banks credit administration factor is 4.108, this value std. Deviation 0.50303 is closed to tall. As a result, the bank's credit management and performance are the most Cause for project disappointment or failure.

4.6. SOCIO-POLITICAL ENVIRONMENT FACTORS AND PROJECT FAILURE
TABLE 4.15 DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS SOCIO-POLITICAL ENVIRONMENT
FACTORS

Social unrest and asset damage	Mean	Std. Deviation
	4.0881	0.609615
Political violation	4.1250	.54272
Looting of investment asset	4.0909	.61842
Movement restriction	4.0341	.63334
Burning of projects investment	4.1023	.64398
Movement restrictions Because of Corona Virus	4.1523	0.579046
Communication problem with supplier	4.0455	.56546
Import export difficulty	4.2614	.61578
Machinery installation by foreign expert not handle as per agreement	4.1818	.57825
Project commissioning testing not handle as per Agreement	4.1932	.58443
Grand Mean	4.1237	0.59433

Source: own survey SPSS output 2024

As shown within the over table 4.15 the mean value of It appears/shows that it has 9 questions in two measurements, with answers extending from social distress and resource harm/damage Mean=4.0881(S. D = 0.50694). Crown Infection Mean=4.1523 (S-D=0.579046). Respondents are development bank of Ethiopia and project administration staff who replied questions on a scale of 1 to 5. each variable is greater than 4. It implies that most of the respondents are high on the impacts of socio- political calculate for project failure. In expansion to this the amazing mean of the variable is 4.1237. It is near too high. As you're all mindful, the years 2020 and 21 saw a number of residential and international financial and political instabilities that hurt especially the monetary division. In this respect, the continuation of COVID 19 and its knock-on impacts, which have without a doubt rocked the establishments of the worldwide/global economy, the instability experienced in our country, the spike in expansion, the lack of foreign money/currency, the delay in accepting supplies of machinery, the lack of control and outages, and other related factors were a few of the difficulties we confronted in our yearly report due on

(June 30, 2022). The result of this research has comparative/similar finding with Vicente et al, (2018) cited by Laguna, (2022) for social distress problems for project disappointment/failure. As shown within the over table social unrest issues/problem around the venture/project region a Cause for project failure. Essentially, Vicente et al, (2018) cited by Laguna, (2022), has conducted inquire about with the title of investigating project complexity through project disappointment by utilizing clustering techniques. The same has been happened in Ethiopia in recent a long time, due to political issues there's no peace, security and stability within the nation.

Agreeing to Teferi, (2020), After analyzing the socio-political scene, it has been decided that corruption and political interference are significant factors contributing to project failures. Issues and intervention of political leaders on project is an identified cause for project disappointment/failure.

4.7. SUMMARY OF DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS RESPONSES ON INDEPENDENT AND DEPENDENT VARIABLES

TABLE 4.16, SUMMARY OF DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

	Project failure	Project Specific factors	Bank’s Credit Management Factors	Socio- political Environment Factors
N	88	88	88	88
Minimum	1.00	2.50	1.94	3.23
Maximum	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00
Std. Deviation	.84387	.40255	.49136	.31566
Mean	4.0227	4.0787	4.1176	4.1202

Source: own survey SPSS output 2024

Table 4.16 shows the average pointers of variables computed from questionnaire information by utilizing/using SPSS and the standard deviation that shows how much scattering exists from the average value. Agreeing to Wang, et al (2019), a low standard deviation shows that the information point tends to be very near to the mean, while high standard deviation shows that the information point is spread out over a huge range of values. As can be displayed within the table 4.16, the mean values of particular project failure factor have a mean value of 4.0787 and a standard deviation of 0.40255. The mean for banks credit administration was 4.1176, with a 0.49136 standard deviation. The mean for macro- financial factor was 4.1091 standard deviation (0.56804).

The cruel value of socio-political features a mean value 4.1202 and standard deviation (0.31566). All the factors are greater than 4. This implies that all factors have tall impact for project disappointment. Based on the questionnaire organize/format (1=very low, 2=low, 3= medium, 4= high and 5= very high) based on this all the over factors within the table has mean value more than 4. As a result, project implementation issues, administration problems, quality of products issues, examination issues, devaluation of local support, follow-up issues, social distress and crown infection were the foremost causes for project disappointment. For the most part, projects particular factors banks administration factors, macro-economic factors and socio environmental factors are the most reason for project fall level.

4.8. CORRELATION ANALYSIS

TABLE 4.17. CORRELATION

		Project Specific	Bank's Credit Management	Socio-political Environment	Project failure
Project Specific	Pearson Correlation	1			
	Sig.(2-tailed)				
	N	88			
bank's Credit Management	Pearson Correlation	.676**.	1		
	Sig.(2-tailed)	.000			
	N	88	88		
	Sig.(2-tailed)	.000	.000		
	N	88	88		
Socio-political Environment	Pearson Correlation	.390**	.532**	1	
	Sig.(2-tailed)	.000	.000		
	N	88	88	88	
Project Failure	Pearson Correlation	.704**	.719**	.575**	1
	Sig.(2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	88	88	88	88

Source: spss output 2024

The significance of a relationship/correlation coefficient of a specific size will alter depending on the measure of the sample from which it was computed. The values of the correlation coefficient are continuously between -1 and +1. A relationship/correlation coefficient of +1 indicates that the two variables are impeccably related positively; whereas a correlation coefficient of -1 demonstrates that two variables are perfectly related in a negative straight/linear sense. A correlation coefficient of 0, on the other hand demonstrates that there's no straight relationship between two variables (Gujarati, 2004). The correlation result in Table 4.17, shows that all independent variables are positively connected to dependent variable. Which means when project particular factors (project implementation issue, administration issue and quality of product and marketing issues), bank's credit administration factors (evaluation issue, issue of finance release and follow-up issues), macro-economic components (devaluation of local cash and exchange rate) and socio environmental factors (social unrest and crown infection) are increased more projects will be failed. More over venture particular calculate encompasses a correlation coefficient 0.704 with high significant level.

This implies the project particular factors such as project implementation issues, administration issues and quality of item and marketing issues are caused for project failure by correlation coefficient of 0.704 and the second variable bank's credit administration factors (evaluation issue, finance release issue and follow-up issues) cause the project disappointment/failure by the relationship coefficient 0.719 with tall significant level.

The third independent variable is macro-economic factor which influence the project by the correlation coefficient of 0.575 and the final variable socio-political environmental factor (social unrest and covid-19) cause the project failure by correlation coefficient of 0.57.

4.9. REGRESSION RESULT

TABLE 4.18, REGRESSION RESULT

Coefficients ^a									
Model	Unstandardized		Standardized	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error				Beta	Lower Bound		
1 (Constant)	-4.655	.752	-	-6.187	.000	-6.151	-3.158	-	
Project Specific factor	.683	.181	.326	3.769	.000	.322	1.043	.510	1.962
Bank's Credit Management factor	.448	.160	.261	2.794	.006	.129	.767	.436	2.293
Socio-political Environment factor	.660	.195	.247	3.384	.001	.272	1.048	.715	1.398
A. Dependent Variable: project failure									

Source: SPSS output 2024

Under regression examinations it's important to make sure that there's low co-linearity, the values of Resistance/tolerance and VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) should be checked.

Tolerance indicates to what extent the independent variables don't clarify much of the variability of an indicated independent variable and the value should be more than 0.10 to demonstrate the nonappearance of co-linearity. In addition to that, VIF, the inverse of tolerance value, should have a value of less than 10 to maintain a strategic distance from any concerns of co-linearity (Pallant, 2007) cited by Mathewos (2019), By and large VIF over 4 and tolerance below 0.25 has multi-col-linearity (needs further examination). Hence, the values within the table 4.18, over demonstrate low co-linearity since all Resilience values are over 0.1 and all VIF values are less than 10.

Subsequently, these tests reflect that the factors used within the think about are free from multi co-linearity.

4.10. REGRESSION MODEL TESTS

4.10.1. MULTIPLE-REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Regression analysis is a prediction model that we fit to our data to forecast values for the dependent variable from one or more independent variables (Field, 2005). Multiple regressions were employed by the researcher to forecast the results of independent variables. The researcher must employ multiple regression models when there are two or more independent variables in the investigation. The impact of different project failure (Bank Credit Management, Project-Specific Socio-Political Environment) on factors affecting for project failure the case of development bank of Ethiopia financed projects is investigated using multiple linear regression analysis.

The two sets of variables included in this study's equation for multiple regressions are the project failure dependent variable and the (Bank Credit Management, Project-Specific Macroeconomic Environment, Socio-Political) independent variable. Regression analysis was used in this study with the primary goal of improving the researcher's ability to predict the given variables.

4.10.2. TEST FOR HOMOSCEDASTICITY

The presumption of homoscedasticity is that the residuals are roughly/approximate rise to for all anticipated subordinate variable scores- the variance of errors is constant, in case the presumption are met the design of the residuals were have almost the same spread on either side of a horizontal line drawn through the average residual Wooldridge (2005).

Something else, in the event that the errors don't have a consistent variance, they are said to be heteroscedastic. Information is homoscedastic on the off chance that the residuals plot is the same width for all values of the anticipated.

Source: SPSS output 2024

FIGURE 4.2, HETEROSCEDASTIC

The over chart implies that it is heteroscedastic means that the errors don't have a consistent variance and mean isn't zero. Heteroscedasticity is usually shown by a cluster of focuses that's wider as the values for the predicted subordinate/dependent variable get larger. The residuals plot shows data that are not spread with the same width all over the average remaining. Within the over figure all specks are not in constant distance and mean. In this manner, it fulfills heteroscedasticity test. In addition, the residuals plot appears information that meet the assumptions of heteroscedasticity.

4.10.3. TEST FOR MULTI CO-LINEARITY

TABLE 4.19, MULTI CO-LINEARITY

Dependent Variable: Failed projects (projects failure)

Model	Independent variable	Co-linearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	Project Specific	.510	1.962
	bank's Credit Management	.436	2.293
	Socio-political Environment	.715	1.398

Source: own survey SPSS output 2024

Under regression investigations it's important to form sure that there's low co-linearity, the values of Tolerance and VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) ought to be checked. Tolerance indicates to what extent the independent variables don't clarify much of the variability of an indicated independent variable and the value ought to be more than 0.10 to show the non-attendance of co-linearity. In expansion to that, VIF, the inverse of tolerance value, ought to have a value of less than 10 to maintain a strategic distance from any concerns of co-linearity (Pallant, 2007) cited by Mathews (2019), By and large VIF over 4 and tolerance below 0.25 has multi-collinearity (needs encourage examination). Subsequently, the values within the table 4.19, over demonstrate moo co-linearity since all Tolerance values are over 0.1 and all VIF values are less than 10. Subsequently, these tests reflect that the factors utilized within the study are free from multi co-linearity.

4.10.4. TESTS FOR AUTOCORRELATION, NORMALITY AND LINEARITY

The autocorrelation assumption is made of the numerous liner regression's unsettling influence terms is that the covariance between the mistake/error terms over time is zero; it assumed that the errors are uncorrelated with one another. In the event that the errors are not uncorrelated with one another, it would be expressed that they are seriously correlated. It tests a relationship between an error term and its immediately past value.

TABLE 4.20, MODEL SUMMARY

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson	
1	.827 ^a	.684	.669	.48550	1.510	
A. Predictors: (Constant), Socio-political Environment, Project Specific, bank's Credit Management						
B. Dependent Variable: project failure						

Source: SPSS output 2024

Testing whether the residuals are normally distributed requires compromise the estimation of coefficients and the calculation of confidence intervals. In some cases, the error distribution is "skewed" by the nearness of expansive exceptions. Since parameter estimation is based on the minimization of squared error, a few extraordinary perceptions can exert an unbalanced impact on parameter estimates. Calculation of confidence intervals and different importance tests for coefficients are all based on the presumptions that the value of DW statistic ranges from 1 to 4.

As a general rule of thumb, the residuals are not correlated in the event that the DW result is approximately 2, and the acceptance range is 1.50 to 2.50. As a result of table 4.18 the autocorrelation of the factors/variables is positive autocorrelation DW states that in case the value is between 1 and 2, they have positive relations.

In arrange to decide normality graphically we will utilize the output of a normal Q-Q Plot. In case the information is normally dispersed, at that point the data focuses were near to the diagonal (horizontal) line. In case the information focuses stray from the line in a self-evident non-linear design, at that point the data are not normally distributed. As we will see from the SPSS yield, figure 4.2 underneath and the data are normally distributed.

Source: SPSS output 2024

FIGURE 4.3. TEST OF NORMALITY

Infringement of linearity are extremely serious in case the model accommodates nonlinear information, forecasts are likely to be seriously in error, particularly when extrapolate beyond the range of the sample data. Nonlinearity is usually most evident in a plot of the observed versus predicted values or a plot of residuals versus predicted values, which are a portion of standard regression output. The focuses ought to be symmetrically disseminated around a diagonal line within the previous plot or a horizontal line within the last-mentioned plot.

4.10.5. SUMMARY OF REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Further test is needed to identify variables that are cause for project failure. Multiple Liner regression was done to examine whether such relationship existed. Two regressions were run, the results of which are presented in next tables.

TABLE 4.21: ANOVA^A

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	42.390	4	10.598	44.960	.000^b
	Residual	19.564	83	.236		
	Total	61.955	87			

Source: Survey SPSS 2024

A. Dependent Variable: -project failure/disappointment.

B. Indicators/predictors: -Bank Credit Management, Project-Specific Environment, Socio- Political Environment.

Indicators: - Bank Credit Management, Project-Specific Environment, Socio-Political Environment as a Source The sig value 0.0 is more prominent than the calculated sig agreeing to the ANOVA test within the table. Value 0.000. This appears that, at the 1% level of significance, there was a statistically significant correlation between the dependent and independent variables. Explanatory variable is what it is called. bank credit management are the social and political environment The discoveries/findings in Table 4.21, illustrate the high statistical significance of the F-value (44.960), which incorporates a p-value of 0.00. As a result, the model was suitable and reliable for calculating the sector's payout ratio.

TABLE 4.22, MODEL SUMMARY

Multiple R	R Square	Adjusted R Square
.827 ^a	.684	.669

Source: Survey SPSS 2024

A. Dependent Variable: - project disappointment/failure

B. Indicators: (Constant), Socio-political Environment, Project Particular, bank's Credit Management.

Agreeing to the result, balanced R-square value was 0.669 as shown in table 4.20, of the model summary. of the change within the dependent variable can be credited to the independent variable's change. Appropriately, 66.9% of projects fail due to socio-political environment, particular project failure variables, and bank credit management capability. The remaining 33.1% of performance varieties can be clarified by other variables.

TABLE 4.23, COEFFICIENTS

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1(Constant)	-4.655	.752		-6.187	.000
Project Specific	.683	.181	.326	3.769	.000
bank's Credit Management	.448	.160	.261	2.794	.006
Socio-political Environment	.660	.195	.247	3.384	.001

Source: SPSS output 2024

4.11. PROJECT SPECIFIC FACTORS AND PROJECT FAILURE

From the above table 4.23, depicted that, the coefficient of project specific factors (which includes project implementation problems, management problems and quality of products and marketing problems) and project failure is 0.006. Holding other independent variables constant at their average value, when project specific factors (project implementation problems, management problems and quality of products and marketing problems) increased by 1%, probability of project failure of sampled financed projects by development bank of Ethiopia would be increased by 68.3%.

In other words, there is significant positive relationship between project specific factors which includes project implementation problems, management problems and quality of products and marketing problems and projects failure. Therefore, the researcher does not accept the hypothesis that the project related factors project implementation delay, management problems and quality of products and marketing problems have no significant impact for project failure in the case of Development Bank of Ethiopia financed projects.

As a result, the project specific factors like project implementation delay, management problems and quality of products and marketing problems have significant impact for project failure in the case of Development Bank of Ethiopia financed projects.

4.12. BANK'S CREDIT MANAGEMENT FACTOR AND PROJECT FAILURE

Table 4.23, above delineated that, the coefficient of project particular factors (which includes project implementation issues, management issues and quality of products and marketing issues) and project disappointment is 0.683 and its P-value is 0.000. Holding other independent variables consistent at their average value, when project particular factors (project implementation issues, management issues and quality of products and marketing issues) increased by 1%, probability of project failure of sampled financed projects by development bank of Ethiopia would be increased by 68.3%, It is statistically critical at 5% of significance level.

In other words, there's significant positive relationship between project particular components which includes project implementation issues, management problems and quality of products and marketing issues and projects failure. The result of the record examination report affirms that the three fundamental project-specific related causes of project failure are management issues, market and marketing issues, and delays in project implementation. Subsequently, the analyst does not accept the hypothesis that the project related factors project implementation delay, administration issues and quality of products and marketing issues have no significant affect for project failure in the case of Development Bank of Ethiopia financed ventures. Subsequently, the invalid hypothesis will acknowledge. As a result, the project particular variables like project implementation delay, administration issues and quality of products and marketing issues have significant affect for project disappointment in the case of Development Bank of Ethiopia financed projects.

4.13. SOCIO-POLITICAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL FACTOR AND PROJECT FAILURE

Socio-political and environmental factor and project disappointment have positive and significant relationship at 5% level of significance. SPSS result within the above table 4.15 appears that the coefficient of Socio- political and environmental factor is 0.660. it is statistically noteworthy with p value of 0.001 at 5% significant.

This implies that on average, when Socio-political and environmental variables (like social turmoil and covid-19) increment by 1%, project failure will increase by 66%. As you're all mindful, a long time 2021 and 23 saw a number of domestic and international socio economic and political instabilities that hurt especially the financial sector. In this respect, the continuation of COVID 19 and its knock-on impacts, which have without a doubt shaken the establishments of the worldwide economy, the instability experienced in our nation, the spike in inflation, the lack of foreign currency, the delay in accepting supplies of machinery, the lack of power and outages, and other related factors were a few of the difficulties we confronted in our yearly report development bank of Ethiopia due on (June 30, 2021).

4.14. GENERAL DISCUSSION

As has been expressed in chapter one the general objective of this study was to distinguish cause of project failure Advance, the research theory has been formulated under chapter two based on the general objective and the conceptual outline work. The research hypothesis has grouped in to four continence, project particular related factors, banks credit management related factors, macro-economic related variables and socio-political environment factors. From the project particular factors, poor project implementation, management issue and quality of product and marketing issues has been analyzed. Management issue, poor implementation, technical failure, market and marketing issue, financial indebtedness of the promoter, and quality of man power failure, lost objectives and poor administration are factors for project failure from project specific factors Alex (2018). Because it can be seen within the over table 4.12 from project particular factors all project implementation issues, project administration issue and item quality and marketing issues are statically significant since their particular P-value below 5 %. Based on this result the invalid hypothesis is accepted; project particular factors have significant affect for project failure.

As you're all mindful, the years 2022 and 21 saw a number of domestic and international socio financial and political instabilities that hurt especially the financial sector. In this regard, the continuation of COVID 19 and its knock-on impacts, which have without a doubt rocked the foundations of the global economy, the instability experienced in our country, the spike in inflation, the lack of foreign currency, the delay in receiving supplies of machinery, the lack of power and outages, and other related factors were a few of the challenges we confronted in our yearly report due on (June 30, 2022).

Poor money related capacity, inaccurate costing and corruption, incompetence and lack of information, poor arranging and estimation, poor communication, poor contracting and contractor practices and frequent plan scope changes are causes for project failure in developing country (Lord & MANU, 2019).

Over estimation of cash flow of projects during evaluation has significant affect for project failure for projects financed by development bank of Ethiopia. There's significant relationship of project follow up and project failure for ventures financed by Development Bank of Ethiopia (Yilkal 2018).

After the fulfillment of all the specified documents by the borrower and know your customer arranged by the bank, examination work conducted. During evaluation the bank's examination performer either over evaluate or under assess. When over evaluation happen the credit burden of the project gets to be high and incapable to settle the credit, when under evaluation the planned project may not actualize as expected and gets to be failed project. The other examination issues watched on DBE financed projects are assessing with current cost as it were, lost investment items, brief implementation plan, no possibility planning and assessing projects by using unreal data. From loan disbursement time up to completely repaid of the disbursed loan, the bank under takes regular follow ups and gives technical advice as per the discoveries. For project as of now begun operation and healthy the bank conduct follows up twice per year and for under implementation projects four times per year. The bank has diverse experts from diverse discipline.

The purpose of having diverse discipline is to provide technical advice for financed projects. In any case, due to time limitation or careless act of the follow up performers no regular follow up conducted, utilized unreal follow up information and report because it is, incapable to distinguish potential dangers and also the follow up team may not inform the follow up discoveries to the project proprietor are the issues for project failure.

Because it can be seen within the above table 4.13 from bank's related independent factors "Project examination problems and Project follow up and technical advice factors statistically significant since their individual p-values are less than 5%, the level of significance. From the discoveries, it can be encouraged concluded that, Project evaluation issues have positive relationship with project disappointment the same follow-up & technical advice issues have positive relationship with project disappointment, this result shows that when project examination issue is high the development bank of Ethiopia financed projects failed more and when project take after up and specialized counsel decreased development bank of Ethiopia financed ventures fizzled.

The finding is comparative to Lord M. AND MANU, (2019). The finding of project evaluation issue is additionally the same with (Yilkal 2018). Be that as it may, the finding of this research for project take after up and technical counsel has inverse result with the finding, The current finding is that, project takes after up and specialized counsel issues given to the clients by the bank has significant affect for project disappointment however the result of expressed there's no noteworthy relationship of project take after up and venture disappointment for ventures financed by Improvement Bank of Ethiopia. From bank's credit management hone, fund release factor isn't statistically noteworthy, which is not consistent to the finding of Richard, (2012) he distinguished those delays within the release of funds and frequent interference by policy makers, inappropriate obtainment process and arranging without association of partners are the factors for project failure in developing nation.

For the right implementation and operation of projects stable macro-economic environment ought to be exist. From the macro-economic factors accessibility of foreign currency and stable exchange rate are very essential. For imported investment things the bank designate budget with the current date or at the reporting date of examination, not as it were imported things but too payments for foreign experts arranged by the rate at the announcing date. In any case, the accessibility of foreign currency very limited and the exchange rate highly expanded from time to time.

As per the secondary data collected from the project follow up reports of development bank of Ethiopia financed projects deficiency of foreign currency and exchange rate increase, projects not implemented and worked as per the arrange and entered in to failed project continence.

In any case, as shown within the above table 4.14 macro-economic factors are statistically significant since its individual p-value is below 5% noteworthy level. The result is reliable with the finding of Alex (2018).

The result of this investigate has comparative finding with Vicente et al., (2018) cited by Laguna, (2022) for social unrest issues for project failure. As appeared within the above table social unrest issues around the project range has positive significant impact for project failure. So also, Vicente et al., (2018) cited by Laguna, (2022 has conducted research with the title of investigating project complexity through project disappointment by utilizing clustering procedures. The consider has 5 clusters and under 5th cluster political, social, economic or legitimate changes has tall impact on project failure.

The same has been happened in Ethiopia in later a long time, due to political issues there's no peace, security and stability within the country. Based on the study's comes about, development bank of Ethiopia and project administration staff the project particular figure (Mean = 4.0787, SD = 0.040255). The feature that was least bank credit administration (Mean = 4.1176; SD = 0.49136). in the socio-political factor decretive result mean value 4.1202and (standard deviation,0.31566). The study's findings show that there's a significant relationship between the in Indicators:

(Constant), Socio-political Environment, Project Specific, bank's Credit Administration ($r = 0.575$ p-value = 0.00) and ($r = 0.575$, p-value = 0.000), ($r=0.704$, p-value=000 ($r=0.719$ p-value 0.000 separately. The Pearson relationship analyses were utilized to set up this relationship. The regression investigation uncovered that the free factors of particular extend calculate bank credit management and socio politic al factor clarified 66.9% of the variability within the dependent variable of project failure, with a balanced R-square esteem of 0.669. The remaining 33.1% of the variability was different from what was predicted by this show.

The current investigates finding measured the effect of these factors for project failure. In like manner, the occurrence of social unrest has noteworthy impact as appeared within the above table 4.15, consequently the research hypothesis rejected. From socio-political factors the event of Corona infection has significant impact for development bank of Ethiopia financed projects as per this consider.

4.17. SUMMARY OF THE REGRESSION ANALYSIS

TABLE 4.22. SUMMARY OF REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Independent Variables	Expected impact (hypothesis)	Actual result	Statically
Project specific factors	No impact	Significant and Positive impact	Significant
bank's credit management factors	No impact	Significant and Positive Impact	Significant
Socio Political and environmental factors	No impact	Significant and Positive Impact	Significant

Source: SPSS 2024

4.18. DATA GATHERED FROM CONDUCTED INTERVIEW

As the meet/interview made with diverse/different people who has great background to the study, they have given the taking after causes as the reason why projects come up brief in DBE. Most of the respondents have worked more than 6 a long time of experience (76.4%). Most of the respondent's obligation may be a master/expert (81.3%). At the development projects drop flat or weakened since of organization related components such as require of aptitude/skill, data and experience. From diverse project disillusionment components Organization related disappointment/failure variables such as organization aptitudes/ability and experience, communication, administration support, client association, sense of proprietorship and nonstop checking/observing and controlling issues are the genuine/series causes of project disappointment/failure which is caused by building poor administration practice. Most of the respondents replied that financial relate components/factors doesn't impact ventures. Most of the respondents answered that money related variables impact projects through Working capital and high fund.

Most of the respondents replied nearly the mode of project finance that's supplier financed and the budget of each project is 600 million dollar, SLM 450 million Dollar, participatory small-scale expand 320 million Dollar and Creature/animal items/products quality wander 430 million Dollar (86.4%). of the respondents. Organization related components impact projects is communicated in terms of destitute/poor coordination between the partners, destitute/poor communication, no supportive gestures and inspirations from the beat organization are the causes for project disappointment/failure.

Exterior/outside related variables/factors such as political environment through government intercession, social environment through social guidelines and values, mechanical environment through requires of utilizing advanced advances/technologies and client through disappointment/failure by the venture/project achievements are besides causes of project disappointment inside the organization. About interviewee looks project executive related and venture group individuals related variables/factors are as the major cause of disappointment of project inside the organization. All of the ventures are nearly more than 6 a long-time length i.e. moment/second circular project time.

CHAPTER FIVE

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. INTRODUCTION

This chapter deals with to summarize the findings of a research just after the appropriate data presentation, analysis and interpretation of the findings. In the previous chapter, the required discussion has been carried out in detail by using the results and findings of the data. Various statistical tools and techniques have been adapted to process and analyze the collected data. This section of the study attempts to summarize the findings, draw conclusions and to provide the required recommendations.

5.2. CONCLUSION

Studying the primary factors of project failure at the Development Bank of Ethiopia headquarters was the primary goal of this study. This study's specific goal was to evaluate the bank-related, socio-environmental, project-specific, factors that contributed to the head office of the Development Bank of Ethiopia's project failure. Discussions, analyses, and interpretations have been conducted in addition to the demonstration of the data collection results. Based on the characteristics of the data, the discussion and analysis portion were divided into two main sections in the previous section in an attempt to convey the findings. The results of the primary data were thoroughly discussed in the descriptive analysis section, while the model was estimated in the quantitative analysis section.

Overall, the main factors of the project's failure have been determined in the second section. A reliability test was conducted on each questionnaire to determine its level of reliability before moving on to the main analysis of the study. The results showed that all of the questionnaires were acceptable and reliable, with a Cronbach's Alpha score of 0.843. Subsequently, in light of the results thus far discussed, descriptive statistics were created in order to evaluate the respondents' information and the project's current state. Additionally, a multi-co-linearity test was conducted.

As suggested by N.A.M.R & T.M.J.A. (2019), the multicollinearity diagnosis table additionally demonstrated that no value is greater than 0.8, indicating that the variables used in the study are free from multicollinearity. The results show that all tolerance values are above 0.1 and all VIF values are less than 10.

In addition, the result of calculated relapse examination was made and it show that autonomous variable like Venture evaluation issues, venture take after up issues and social turmoil have essentially impact for venture disappointment. By and large, the consider endeavors to recognize the causes for extend disappointment by collecting information from Development bank of Ethiopia financed ventures administration staffs and Improvement Bank of Ethiopia credit entertainers. Appropriately, recognizing the causes for venture disappointment is exceptionally basic to realize the crave objective of the ventures as per desire of the proprietors, the Bank and the nation in common.

By and large, the significant causes or factors for project failure are recorded underneath.

- From The extend related variables; project usage delay, administration issues and quality of items and promoting issues have noteworthy affect for venture disappointment within the case of Development Bank of Ethiopia financed projects.
- Bank's credit administration issues like examination issue, support discharge delay and need of legitimate extend take after up are noteworthy factors of ventures disappointment within the case of development Bank of Ethiopia financed ventures or projects.
- From Socio-political and natural variables; social distress and occurrence of Crown infection widespread have noteworthy affect for extend/projects disappointment or failure within the case of Development Bank of Ethiopia financed projects.

5.3. RECOMMENDATION

Based on the research revelations the examiner proposes the taking after recommendations to decrease or guarantee expand disappointment. Since amplify assessment issue is recognized as significant factor of amplify disappointment and project organizing is essential for project success at the essential organize the bank ought to carefully conduct the assessment get ready, National bank of Ethiopia need to take after banks and set reasonable motivations and managements of the ventures/projects might assign the specified investment taken a toll, surveying extend utilizing current cost, distribute possibility budget, assessing without misplaced wander things, evaluate ventures by utilizing veritable data or information and orchestrate adequate implantation period or elegance period.

Project management Introduction visit and encounter sharing programs to neighborhood project managers/owners to move forward or improve their promoting or knowledge.

- ❖ The other the figure for project disappointment recognized by this study is project take after up and specialized counsel issue. After give the loan, the bank shall embrace regular project take after up and gives specialized advice to the customer based on the take after up discoveries. Be that as it may, as this study finding appears the venture/projects take after ups not conduct as per the plan, the take after up group creates the report without approve the collected information, which demonstrate the capacity problem of the take after up performers, the bank too not give appropriate technical counsel based on the take after up discoveries and proposals. And consequently, the bank should act the project take after up as per the arrange by putting take after up standards.
- ❖ From the analyzed free factors social turmoil from socio political environment factors too has significant impact for venture disappointment. So as project implant and work with the assistance of the society and it's clear the projects offer assistance that society either specifically or in a roundabout way the society ought to keep and the extend when political or social distress happen. So, amid such circumstance happen, or some time recently happen mindfulness creation ought to obligatory, the concerned government organ should to ensure the speculation ventures by allotting committed security around the area. Project managers must watch the environment some time recently venture begin work. The analyst prescribed that the financier bank and the extend proprietors might in put chance preoccupation some time recently by obtaining protections scope.
- ❖ Finally, the researcher too prescribed/recommended encourage investigate by utilizing other research strategies for insignificant factors of this study.

5.4. IMPLICATION FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

This research has certain limitations because it was conducted during a period of financial lockup and unrest. While answering the questionnaire, participants may experience anxiety about their circumstances and a lack of freedom, which may have an indirect bearing on the study's conclusions. Therefore, it is advised to conduct additional research by gathering information from subjects who are not afraid of this kind of thing.

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APPENDIX I

Appendices/Attachments

Appendix1: QUESTIONNAIRE Gage University College

College of Project management department

QUESTIONNAIRE: -

Researcher: Shegaw Abishu (email:shegawabishu7@gmail.com)

Research Topic: The factors affecting of project failure: in case Development Bank of Ethiopia projects

Dear Respondents: -

I would like to express my earnest appreciation for your generous time, honest and prompt responses to participate on this survey questionnaire and this questionnaire is designed to collect data about the “factor affecting for project failure the case of Development Bank of Ethiopia financed projects. The information that you offer me with this questionnaire was used as a primary data in my study which I am conducting as partial fulfillment of their requirements for the MSc in Project management. Therefore, this research is to be evaluate in terms of its Contribution to our understanding of factors for project failure in the case of projects financed Development Bank of Ethiopia.

General Instructions: -

- No need of writing your name.
- In all cases where answer options are available, please tick (✓) in the appropriate box.

Confidentiality:-I want to assure you that this research is only for academic purpose authorized by the GAGE University College Department of Project Management No other person will have to access this collected data. If you have any queries concerning the questionnaire, please contact me:

- Name: Shegaw Abishu,
- Phone Number: +251939175106
- Email: shegawabishu7@gmail.com)

Thank you for your Cooperation's

**Part I. This part of the questionnaire covers items related to
background of the respondents.**

❖ (Please put (√) or (X) in the appropriate boxes); Name of the project _____

1. Gender of respondents.

a. Male b. Female

2. Please indicate your education all level.

a. Diploma c. MA or MSc

b. BA or BSc d. PhD

3. Age:

A. Below 20 years

c. 26-35 years

b. 20-25 years

d. 36-45 years Above 45

If other please specify.....

3. Type of the project.

a. Manufacturing

c. Mining

b. Agriculture

d. Service

4. Form of the company.

a. Sole proprietorship

c. Corporation

b. PLC

5. Please indicate your current position in the project/Bank.

a. Owner/shareholder

e. Loan officer

b. General Manager

f. Senior loan officer

c. Team Manager

g. Senior Expert

d. Project Manager

h. Junior Expert

Others specify _____

6. Please indicate your religious

a. Orthodox

d. Muslim

b. Catholic

c. Protestant

Others

specify _____

7. Please indicate your marital statuses.

a. Single c. Window

b. Married

8. Please indicate your work experience in the industry.

a. Less than 2 year's

c. 2-3 years

b. 4-6 years

d. More than 6 years

If other please specify.....

9. Please indicate your experience in the project/bank.

a. Less than 2 years

c. 2-3 years

b. 4-6 years

d. More than 6 years

If other please specify.....

10. Please indicate the experience of the company in the business.

a. Less than 2 years

c. 2-3 years

b. 4-6 years

d. More than 6 years

If other please specify.....

Part.2. Question related the status of the project

1. Questions Related to Project Specific factors that contribute for Project failure

➤ Please select the best scale that best describe your response and put “√” mark

Very low=1, = low =2, medium = 3, high= 4, very high = 5

1. Please describe to what extent the following factors contribute for project failure.

Project implementation Problems	1	2	3	4	5
➤ Experience or exposure to implement the project					
➤ Procurement Knowledge gap					
➤ Risk, Assessment, Skill Limitation					
➤ Decision making ability					
➤ Resource Management Skill					
➤ Communication skill					
Management Problem	1	2	3	4	5
➤ Hiring Relatives					
➤ Experience of Management Staff					
➤ Educational Qualification					
➤ Leadership problem					
Quality of products and marketing problem	1	2	3	4	5
• Absence of Quality control					
• Use of obsolete technology					
• Unavailability of quality raw material					
• Stiff market competition					
• No bargaining power in the international market					

Please list project specific factors that contributes for project failure if any more?

2. Questions Related to the bank’s Credit Management factors that contribute for Project failure.

➤ Please select the best scale that best describe your response and put “√” mark Very low---

1, low---2, medium---3, high---4, very high----5

1. Please describe to what extent the following factors contribute for project failure.

Appraisal's problem	1	2	3	4	5
• Under appraisal					
• Appraising project with current price only					
• Missing of investment items					
• Short implementation schedule					
• Lack of contingency planning					
• Use of unreal data					
Problem of fund release	1	2	3	4	5
• Equity blocking Problem					
• Unable to fulfill terms and conditions					
• Long process of fund release					
• Capacity of credit performers					
• Unethical act of credit performer					
Follow-up	1	2	3	4	5
• Not conduct follow up as per the plan					
• Data validation problem					
• Risk identification problem during follow-up					
• Capacity problem of follow up performer					
• Limitation to provide technical advice					
• No action as per the follow up recommendation					

Please list bank's Credit Management factors that contribute for project failure if any more.

1. Questions Related to the Socio-political Environment factors that contribute for Project failure

➤ Please select the best scale that best describe your response and put √ mark

Very low----1, low----2, medium----3, high----4, very high----5

1. Please describe to what extent the following factors contribute for project failure.

Social unrest and asset damage	1	2	3	4	5
1. Political violation					
2. Looting of investment asset					
3. Movement restriction					
4. Burning of projects investment					
5. Communication problem with supplier					
6. Import export difficulty					
7. Machinery installation by foreign expert not handle as per agreement					
8. Project commissioning testing not handle as per agreement					

Please list Socio-political Environment factors that contribute for project failure anymore?

2. How much the above-mentioned problems are causes for project failure

- A. Very low B. low C. medium D. high
 E. very high

An Interview Questions on Project failure factors in Ministry of Agriculture and Natural resources will be:

1. How many years have you been in this organization?
2. What is your area of responsibilities in this organization?
3. At the movement projects were failed/stucked and sick. What do you think that the failure causes for projects in your organization?
4. How do economic related factors affect project success in your organization?
5. How do financial related factors affect project success in your organization?
6. How do political related factors affect project success in your organization?
7. How many years is your project duration?

8. From economic, financial, management, technology and human related factors which one is a serious cause for project failure in your organization?
9. Do you think that lack of encouragements and incentives from government is the main causes of project failure in your organization?
10. What are the other factors for project failure in your organization?

APPENDIX II

DOCUMENT ANALYSIS

Development bank of Ethiopia Annual Performance Report. Addis Ababa, Ethiopia Page (09) Annual Report June 30, 2021 and 2022, 2023 Annual Plan and Report, as well as other supporting documentation Literature sources for secondary data.